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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HPC	High-Performance Computing
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IoT	Internet-of-Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
PHIDIAS	Prototype of HPC/Data Infrastructure for On-demand Services
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Deliverable 6.2 of the MOBISPACES project “Use Cases Co-Creation & Design Activities v2” aims to deliver the co-creation activities and design for the different Use Case (UC) scenarios.

This deliverable aims to provide an overview of co-creation and design activities for different UC scenarios, to analyse the requirements of the UCs involved, and to provide refinements whenever deemed necessary, so as to define the subsequent implementation actions.

The first part of the document describes the theoretical approach of co-creation and the role of User Interface (UI)/User Experience (UX) design, suggesting both the methodology and related guidelines to be applied according to the context, i.e., that of co-design, and associated tools, i.e., sketches, wireframes, and mock-ups.

In the second part, the document proceeds to illustrate a description of each of the five UCs. For each UC, we provide a description structured along five axes. First, the objectives of each UC are succinctly presented. Then, more detailed descriptions of UC scenarios are discussed, in an attempt to shed some light on the rationale behind each UC. Thereafter, we present the requirements from the user perspective, offering a high-level view of the required functionality. The next axis concerns the description of datasets per UC, also offering a practical viewpoint of the available information which can be exploited to implement the UC. Finally, the current infrastructure relevant for each UC is presented.

In its third part, the current deliverable presents the progress achieved during the co-creation workshops. This entails both workshops that have already taken place (at the time of this writing) as well as workshops planned for the near future. Tangible examples of the results gathered during co-creation workshops, which were held during the General Assemblies that have already been held, are provided. In this way, we link the co-creation approach with the concrete activities that took place, thus guiding the workplan and the implementation of the project’s UCs.

Overall, this deliverable highlights the key points of the guidelines to make the application of the co-creation process constructive to the project UCs and related scenarios to maximise cooperation and smooth integration among partners.

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1. Introduction

The key objective assigned to this deliverable is to provide an insight into co-creation activities for the different UC scenarios identified within the project.

This document first describes the theoretical approach of co-creation and how it can improve project results. This will help to achieve the objective of identifying a methodology and its related guidelines to be applied according to the context of co-design and associated tools. A specific description is provided of the tools needed to successfully organise a co-creation workshop. Firstly, an analysis is proposed of what are a series of soft skills and organisational abilities that must accompany such a co-creation process and be the founding basis of the spirit behind the organisation of a co-creation event. Secondly, a more detailed view is proposed of what are the possible tools to be employed for a more accurate design of a user interface that emphasises the desired output of the use case: starting with a simple elaboration, through so-called sketches, passing through wireframes, up to potentially arriving at mock-ups that allow for a preview as close as possible to the result. These tools allow a continuous feedback loop during the different development phases.

Moreover, it provides an overview of the five UCs identified within the project. This will help to provide a clear understanding of the goals, objectives and scenarios associated with each one.

The first use case, called iRoute - Intelligent Public Transport Routing, will validate the reliable and transparent data governance framework (WP3) and exploit the mobility analytics results from the mobility-aware edge analytics suite (WP4) to provide intelligent transport services to the public, leveraging the different data collected by AMT.

The second use case, called SmartSense – will approach the domain of air quality management in urban areas by collecting IoT data from air quality sensors in Thessaloniki, model traffic emissions and generate air quality heatmaps. The data will be analysed through the Data Operations Toolbox (WP4) and processed further with the visual analytics toolbox (WP5).

The third use case, called VesselTracker - Edge-powered Vessel Tracking, will validate the decentralised data acquisition and in-situ processing approach described in WP3 and apply the federated learning on edge as well as the visual analytics techniques developed in WP5.

The fourth use case, called VesselEdge - Edge Computing Onboard of Moving Vessels, will validate the mobility-aware learning at the edge approach in the maritime domain and privacy-aware visual analysis operations (WP5). Sensors (AIS receivers) will be installed on moving platforms (vessels) to collect data, using the decentralised data management techniques described in WP4. The validation/impact assessment will be based on the improvements in Vessel Traffic Service (VTS) centre operations.

The fifth use case, called CrowdSeaMapping - Federated learning for Enhancing Depth Data Models, will validate the FL approach developed in WP5 and the decentralised data acquisition and in-situ processing approach described in WP3 to detect anomalies in collected data and verify trustworthiness of existing depth models.

The results of Work Packages 3, 4 and 5 converge within the three architectural pillars defined in Work Package 2 which are outputs of as many tasks, namely the Data Governance Platform, the Data Operations Toolbox and the Edge Analytics Suite. Therefore, all Use Cases, to achieve

their objectives, make use of the results of Work Package 2, which brings together the tools developed in the entire project.

Finally, it outlines the co-creation activities undertaken up to the 16th month. In particular, with the addition of the "Workshops results" section, the contribution made by the co-creation sessions was better structured as they were organised in conjunction with the project General Assemblies: the aim was to provide a bridge between the theory introduced in the "Co-creation theory and tools" section and the practical application in the project with the results obtained. To this end, in addition to the initial brainstorming in Vienna, a complete overview of the work proposed in Lisbon was provided, which was then continued over the following months until today: the introduction of the INVEST criterion made it possible to further refine the User Stories related to scenarios, requirements and datasets of the Use Cases, complementing the previously introduced theory with specific tools.

2. Co-creation theory and tools

This section aims to illustrate the most recently developed theory and methodologies in the field of collaborative work and, thus, the organisation of co-creation workshops (in the first subsection). Then, a series of fundamental concepts to put into practice when organising workshops are analysed for them to be truly productive (second subsection). Finally (third subsection), emphasis is placed on those tools that are widely used today and which can support the practical and user-led realisation of functional interfaces for the use of the tools provided.

All this makes it possible to set up follow-up sessions with the various focus groups to which the Use Cases belong ensuring a better correspondence between requirements and the development feedback obtained.

2.1 Theoretical approach

The term 'co-creation' refers to the process in which the design phase of a product or service is deeply influenced by the contributions made by users, whether in the form of content, ideas, or projects. While this guarantees a practically inexhaustible source of contributions, it also strengthens the link between those who practically create the product/service and those who use it, i.e., in the market context, between company and consumer. However, in the context of MOBISPACES and with reference to the Tasks related to the UCs (Tasks 6.2 – 6.3 – 6.4 – 6.5 – 6.6), the following association can be made:

- partners actively engaged in the development of a UC can be associated with generic customers, making their technical know-how available based on their possibilities;
- the leader, being in direct contact with the end users and the source of the data on which any processing will be possible, can be associated with the generic company.

This approach will be directly reflected in the choice between the different types of co-creation (as defined by O'Hern & Rindfleisch, 2017): indeed, based on the two phases that define all new product development processes, i.e., the contribution (of content) and the selection (of the best contributions), different types of co-creation can be identified. First, a distinction must be made between contributions, which can be fixed or open, and selection, which can be customer or company-driven. Consequently, it is possible to distinguish 4 types of methodological approaches, as seen in Figure 1 taken from (O'Hern & Rindfleisch, 2017):

Figure 1 - Co-creation methodological approaches

- **Collaborating:** In this case, the companies have minimal control, and much is left to the users, such as in the case of communities revolving around open-source software.
- **Tinkering:** Compared to the previous case, contributions are in a lesser form with stricter constraints on the use of the product and its availability, while the company leads the decision-making process in the selection of different creations: a classic example from the software perspective is that of public APIs.
- **Co-designing:** This time, 'co-designers', representing a small group of customers, submit various product designs to the company, while a larger group of customers select the designs that will then actually be produced by the company. Since the requirements for submission are stricter in this case, the classification considers it as a fixed-contribution process, although there are, as mentioned, several 'co-designers'. A well-known example is that of the Lego company with the 'Lego Idea' project: when one project among the several proposed reaches 10000 followers, then the company brings it to the shelves. This method of co-creation appears to be the one most in line with the structure of the present project.
- **Submitting:** In this process the company manages both the mode of contribution and the selection, but the difference from traditional market research lies in the presence of the company's request to several people to propose extremely detailed solutions or projects instead of answering predetermined questions, as is the case with crowdsourcing platforms.

Finally, (Ramaswamy & Ozcan, 2014) identifies four fundamental elements that must be put into practice for any co-creation process to work properly:

- **Access:** Customers must be able to access the data.
- **Dialogue:** Customers can interact with each other and with the company.
- **Risk-benefit:** Monitor risk and gaps between customer and company.
- **Transparency:** Business information is accessible.

2.2 Co-creation workshops: how to improve results properties

From a practical perspective, co-creation takes place during workshops, which can be considered the best way to improve collaboration among involved parties.

The key concept behind co-creation lies in involving people at work so that ideas and concepts are developed collaboratively. Quite literally, co-creation is that process in which designers and users work collaboratively towards a common goal: that is why the co-creation process takes the form of a workshop in which stakeholders explore the problem and identify possible solutions based on different points of view, i.e., approaches and needs. But involvement alone is not enough: everyone must participate actively to have more empathy between the parties, unlike in the traditional UI/UX process. Sharing motivations and emotions during collaborative development promotes constructive dialogues and reflections to achieve the common goal, also inducing greater efficiency in the process. A well-designed co-creation workshop forces:

- A face-to-face discussion of the common problem
- A deeper discovery and understanding of the requirements
- The search for a shared solution

Therefore, co-creation helps to understand what is expected to be achieved so work better and with more focus, hence the initial phase involves concentrating on the minimums and clarifying the essentials such as:

- **Assumptions:** Everyone will have their own idea of how to solve a problem or may have already tried to solve it themselves. To avoid missteps, it is essential to understand the starting assumptions and clarify them in detail so that the right tools can be used in the project. Then you must leave room for the teams to discuss the assumptions and help them turn them into reasonable hypotheses.
- **Background:** If previous experiences with similar projects have caused frustration and mistrust, now is the time to be open so everyone can learn from previous lessons.
- **Beliefs:** Everyone has personal opinions and convictions that are difficult to be shaken, so transparency between teams is a key element for these issues to be addressed carefully. When the divergence of opinions is such that an agreed solution cannot be found, the decision-maker will have to find the best way forward.
- **Expectations:** Everyone has a personal interest in a project and, therefore, different expectations, which can cause problems and slow down the work. Sharing these aspects transparently and understanding each other ensures that the group works towards the same direction.
- **Scope of the project:** When looking for an undiscovered solution to a problem and therefore not knowing how long it will take to solve it, co-creation helps to identify the best steps to be taken in a reasonable timeframe for the teams to work in the best possible way to achieve the objectives.

When the assumptions are clear and have been transformed into reasonable hypotheses, experience has been built upon, and divergent opinions have been identified and resolved, it is time to start benefiting from co-creation, i.e., the opportunity for everyone to provide input and insights to identify and solve the problem. To do this, it is necessary to pinpoint the essential information and skills one has through understanding:

- **Audience:** Who do you address and, who do you not? Empathising with stakeholders in the right way improves the design.
- **Challenges:** They can come during the design process and slow it down, hence being aware of them improves mutual trust and makes teams interact better.
- **Context:** Where the project is located i.e., all the external factors that influence or could influence the products and services you intend to use.
- **Opportunities:** Finding and defining them is not immediate, but exploring new or hidden territories is essential for those who need to understand their work better.
- **Uncovered ingredients:** what you don't know and the open questions that will gradually be integrated will help to get an overview, i.e., the big picture.

Co-creation should not be understood simply as a meeting, but for it to be productive, systematic thinking is required, adequately preparing the event through the presence of:

- **Creators:** Those eager to bring the product/service to life by solving problems.
- **Doers:** Those responsible for the product/service development of the different teams.
- **Decision makers:** Those who make difficult decisions when objectives have not yet been shared between the teams and are responsible for the overall results, as well as for speeding up processes.
- **Experts:** Specialised professionals who contribute with their domain knowledge.
- **Facilitators:** Those who ensure that everything is ready for the sessions, and everyone is comfortable and confident to contribute.

Furthermore, it is crucial to pay attention to:

- **Environment:** A well-prepared space helps team members perform better, making them focus on their inspiration during the creative sessions.
- **Frequency:** It depends on the scope of the project, but it is important that all members stay aligned during co-creation so that they are more involved and can all see feedback and improvements.
- **Fun:** Good humour, which the facilitator will ensure, helps participants feel good and enjoy the teamwork.
- **Methods and tools:** The right tools are essential to capture the key points of the discussions and record them, preventing them from disappearing.
- **Roles:** It is important that they are well defined so that everyone contributes to the co-creation process.
- **Rules:** Electronics and other objects distract people who should instead be fully present with an open mind so that the dialogue is more fluid and constant.
- **Timing:** Avoid workshops close to weekends, preferring Tuesdays (probably the best), Wednesdays and Thursdays, and starting early in the morning before people are pulled into other work issues; do not forget a detailed schedule with breaks and refreshments.

Finally, results need to be made tangible, with periodic updates to involve and empower teams, speeding up the pace and making the process more agile and streamlined. If everything is working properly, certain signs can be noticed, such as the calmness of people in discussing and seeking the best for the project, whereby everyone's commitment and collaboration lead to every change during the project being shared. People feel listened to,

and valued, increasing productivity and feeling part of the project; they share ownership and responsibility.

2.3 Co-creation process: user-driven approach and related tools

Recent years have witnessed a strong development in the field related to Graphical User Interface (GUI) design, which has become increasingly focused on and therefore driven by the weight of user experience. The rapid evolution of the field has led to a proliferation of terminologies and methods that have often been used interchangeably because of the strong correlation between them. At present, however, it is possible to clearly distinguish different types of design products, which are different from each other but useful in the “creation process” through different tools.

Figure 2 - Co-creation process

As can be seen from Figure 2, between the requirements analysis (first step) and the development of the demonstrator (last step), there are critical steps dedicated to the design of the reference architecture and its implementation, which are supported by 3 fundamental tools such as sketches, wireframes and mock-ups that, in that order, represent a gradually more detailed way of structuring the GUI based on ideas and feedback from stakeholders and users, before producing the final prototype at the end of the project.

2.3.1 Sketch

A sketch is defined as a drawing, either created natively digitally or freehand on a sheet of paper, that is intended to provide a basic representation of a concept.

The purpose of such a tool is to provide valuable support in conceptualisation and visualisation at the beginning of the design process. The idea behind it is to take advantage of people's ability to learn visually very quickly and, therefore, be able to provide a conceptual explanation in a more immediate and less articulate manner than is necessary with words.

In this case, the design tool, whatever physical or digital, is intended to facilitate the communication of an idea. Consequently, perfecting such sketches is not useful: approximation with any stencil is welcome if it helps communicate the main idea quickly.

One of the methods that became prominent was the so-called "Crazy Eights", which involves eight sketches of ideas in five minutes, an example of which is shown in Figure 3³.

Figure 3 - Example of "Crazy Eights" sketches

This methodology, which originated within Google Ventures, is due to Jake Knapp, who created the Design Sprint process at Google in 2010 by merging Agile and Design Thinking (Knapp, Zeratsky, & Kowitz, 2016).

In addition, with the development of particularly flexible tools capable of providing interactive prototypes for Android and iOS platforms such as [Marvel POP](#), it has become increasingly relevant to have a digital photo of one's sketches, to be used either as project documentation or as an integral part of a portfolio.

2.3.2 Wireframe

The term "wireframe" refers to any design artefact with low fidelity and the very specific purpose of representing only the most essential elements, i.e., the "wires", hence the name of the user interface. In essence, they constitute the skeleton of the design from which descends the user interface in its most basic version. Therefore, the model from which the final product takes its cue.

³ Source: <https://library.gv.com/the-product-design-sprint-diverge-day-2-c7a5df8e7cd0>

The usefulness of wireframes is greatest at the initial stage of a product design process, as it allows:

- (1) Evaluate the structure that individual pages on the screen will take.
- (2) Understand the correlation between them from the user's point of view.
- (3) Prepare the necessary documentation for design requirements.

Again, they can be created either with pen and paper or with digital tools such as [Balsamiq](https://balsamiq.com), as shown in Figure 4⁴.

Figure 4 - Example of wireframes

Wireframes generally pay no attention to details: their purpose is to provide a solid basis for evaluating the design and essential structure of the product, not its refinement. For example, provided the essential elements for each page to be displayed on the wireframe, a couple of contrasting colours (beyond the traditionally employed black and white) can be chosen to draw attention and place visual emphasis on certain aspects. Also, if there are particularly salient points to be shown to the team, it is a good idea to include timely annotations to create context and convey key ideas quickly, as shown in Figure 5⁵. Sometimes, a clickable wireframe created from the static one helps further.

⁴ Source: <https://balsamiq.com/wireframes/>

⁵ Source: <https://www.behance.net/gallery/45930803/Annotations>

Figure 5 - Example of annotations in wireframes

2.3.3 Mock-up

A design artefact that provides a medium- or high-fidelity visualisation of the project is called a "mock-up." Its task is to provide the visual appearance and evaluate the feelings from the user experience perspective related to the design, as shown in Figure 6⁶.

Figure 6 - Example of mock-ups

The usefulness of a mock-up is evident during the visual design phase of the design process, whether related to a new product or the redesign of something pre-existing. It can provide support for:

⁶ Source: <https://dribbble.com/glebich>

- the assessment of:
 - visual accessibility of the design, i.e., ensuring that every user, regardless of ability, can understand, navigate, and use the product (following W3C recommendations);
 - visual consistency of design, i.e., whether each page on the screen is a part of the whole rather than an individual element;
 - visual layout of the design, i.e., whether the combination of colours, images and typography is well thought out;
- stylistic experimentation, i.e., which colour combination and colour scheme work best for users;
- presentation of the user interface to stakeholders: unlike sketches and wireframes, mock-ups do not require clarification and are immediately comprehensible.

In terms of implementation, the design tools available today are innumerable. Think of [Figma](#), [Sketch](#) and [Photoshop](#) to name the most popular.

Two aspects to keep in mind when creating mock-ups are the following:

- pay attention to the 'Lorem Ipsum', i.e., the fictitious text used to fill mock-ups and which, although it can save time during design, can cause problems when replaced with the real content: additional unplanned work on layouts may be required due to poorly designed mock-ups;
- do not stop at a single design idea, i.e., fall in love with the first idea that seems right and start refining it: this is not the best approach to design. When designing a new product, it is necessary to experiment and try out different solutions, i.e., first develop as many different ideas as possible and then select the best one.

3. Use Cases Overview

This section is used to present the business usage scenarios, providing their UCs or user stories, along with the list of the initial *stakeholder* requirements that have been identified by each of the UCs of the MOBISPACES project. Additionally, it contains information regarding the description of the foreseen datasets that the pilots are planning to bring to the project and any other possible restrictions due to data regulatory constraints.

Firstly, each of the pilots describes the usage of their scenarios from a UC perspective, at a high-level view that will feed the needs for defining their respective *stakeholder* requirements that this report is interested in. It is important to be mentioned that the complete definition of each of the scenarios on a detailed level, including their business aspects and KPIs for their succession, is not the focus of the analysis reported in this document, as this will be carried out under the respective tasks of WP6 (“Use Cases Adaptation, Experimentation & Evaluation”). The scope of this section is to rather provide general descriptions that are more related to the general definition of the behaviour and identification of the important necessities that the architecture should comply with so that they can be considered from the very beginning of the project. The descriptions of the scenarios are complemented with UML Use Case (UC) Diagrams to identify the different actors, prerequisites, and the description of the behaviour.

The following subsections first give an introductory overview of the purpose of each scenario that can help the technical partners quickly understand the needs of the pilot providers. Then, the description of the different user stories that formulate each scenario is presented, along with the corresponding UML diagram, in some predefined templates. Having this user stories definition, then the list of the *stakeholder requirements* has been derived and reported. Then, each of the pilot providers describes the available datasets that will bring to the project, which will drive, among others, the definition of the *Data Management Plan* of MOBISPACES, along with specific aspects of the reference architecture related to the data management activities. Finally, an initial analysis of possible data regulation constraints is provided by each pilot.

3.1 UC#1 iRoute - Intelligent Public Transport Routing (AMT)

3.1.1 Goals and objectives

Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) applications in public transportation have allowed for automated data collection, which is particularly useful for planning and operations, granting better, more informed decisions.

The goal of iRoute UC is to take advantage of the MOBISPACES outcomes set in place and exploit the mobility-aware data governance framework that will utilise the outcomes of analytics related to mobility to drive strategic decisions based on these outcomes. The large amount of data that is continuously collected by many internal and external sources can lead to much more informed real-time fleet management and to optimised maintenance service.

iRoute UC aims to help AMT to realise better performances in electric-fleet operations, both for scheduling and real-time management. To reach this objective, the focus will be on

interlinking data from the bus batteries with data coming from external sources to find ways to have a sort of prediction of the decrease of the battery level.

Another iRoute objective is to reduce malfunctions and optimise maintenance. Even in this case, data collection and analysis can help to predict the main faults that can involve electric buses and manage to repair services in the best way.

The main KPI, which is a target for all the activities of the UC, is to offer a better service to AMT users that may appreciate a reduction of bus waiting, better bus punctuality and a general improvement of their travel experience.

3.1.2 Description of scenarios

A full electric project has been set up by AMT, the public transport company active in the metropolitan city of Genova. In a few years, no more buses with combustion engines will be available in Italy, and many transport operators are considering only green-powered vehicles to renew their fleet: public transport companies are fully involved in the ecological transition of the mobility sector. AMT is a leader in the transition: with almost 100 e-buses, Genova is now the 3rd Italian city considering the number of electric buses.

Managing an electric fleet has peculiar aspects and challenges different from traditional bus fleets. The main issues that AMT would like to investigate regard the following scenarios:

- Improved fleet maintainer operations
- Improved data analysis capabilities
- Improved decision support and fleet allocation

These areas of interest are better detailed in the following tables.

Table 1 - Scenario UC#1-SCE-01

Field	Definition
ID	UC#1-SCE-01
Title	Improved fleet maintainer operations
Description	<p>This scenario regards the maintenance of AMT electric buses. Bus maintenance is now based on deadlines established by law and by bus manufacturers. It often follows faults and malfunctions instead of anticipating them. Predicting malfunctions would help to avoid service disruptions and to manage the fleet in a better way.</p> <p>AMT has a large amount of data about the state of the on-board systems and about the functional parameters of the bus, collected continuously by Canbus installed on board and transmitted daily by the bus to AMT bus monitoring system (called SiMon).</p> <p>Data will be processed to return an optimised maintenance program, that may predict possible malfunctions and schedule the right repair services.</p>
Actors	AMT, ENG
Objectives	To avoid typical malfunctions with a focus on doors and battery temperature

	(fire risk).
Pre-conditions	Maintenance services based on schedule imposed by law or by manufacturer and repair works after faults that occur while the bus is in service, with big negative impact on users.
Process Description	Laws and bus manufacturer instructions → Scheduled maintenance Faults during bus service → Repair
Variations	Laws and bus manufacturer instructions → Scheduled maintenance → Data analysis → Optimization of maintenance plan Data analysis → Predictions of malfunctions → Repair work → No faults during bus service
Post-conditions	Data analysis helps to optimise maintenance plans and to schedule repair interventions that avoid faults and malfunctions during bus service, reducing impact on users.

Table 2 - Scenario UC#1-SCE-02

Field	Definition
ID	UC#1-SCE-02
Title	Improved data analysis capabilities
Description	This scenario is a key step in order to increase the data analysis capabilities with respect to what is available in the AMT infrastructure. The analytical capabilities will support both the other scenarios and any further processing.
Actors	AMT, ENG
Objectives	To make data analysis capabilities available
Pre-conditions	The necessary infrastructure and data must be available for processing
Process Description	Infrastructure up and running → Seamless data uploading and availability → Data processing → Data analytics
Variations	Where no infrastructure and/or data and/or automation is available, variations may be made, such as the use of different infrastructures, different portions of data or different automation
Post-conditions	Improved data analysis capabilities will support any further operational steps

Table 3 - Scenario UC#1-SCE-03

Field	Definition
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ID	UC#1-SCE-03
Title	Improved decision support and fleet allocation
Description	<p>At the moment, electric buses have much lower autonomies than diesel buses. Thus, it is important to carefully face this problem both in real-time operations and in scheduling operations.</p> <p>This scenario heads on data analysis to offer useful information for decisions on the electric bus fleet both for real-time and for scheduling activities. The focus is on the state of charge of the battery and on energy consumption monitoring.</p> <p>Data regarding battery level can be interlinked with other internal data about power absorbed by the engine depending on accelerations, brakes, auxiliary system, and to external data like weather and traffic.</p> <p>Data analysis can give alerts that suggest to the service managers the optimal utilisation of the electric fleet, avoiding that buses circulate with too low battery levels, or must suddenly terminate their service before time, without letting managers organise a proper alternative service for users.</p>
Actors	AMT, ENG
Objectives	To develop bus timesheets following the battery behaviour and decay and to determine the possibility for the bus to end its vehicle schedule with an acceptable battery level.
Pre-conditions	The battery trend is monitored only by the bus driver, who asks for a bus change if the battery level is low. Because of the substitution, users may experience inconvenience due to service interruption.
Process Description	<p>Bus timesheets are created following bus manufacturer indications about battery durations → Especially due to battery decay during years, bus schedules may require too long journeys for the bus, with consequent too-early reduction of battery level</p> <p>Bus driver informs service managers that the battery level of the bus is low → Service managers order bus change → During the bus change the service may be partially disrupted</p>
Variations	<p>Bus timesheets are created following the historical data about battery decay → Bus schedules require the right length of journeys for the bus</p> <p>Data analysis → Interlinking of battery level with other internal and external conditions → Optimised electric fleet management → No inconvenience for users</p>
Post-conditions	Data analysis helps to optimise the creation of bus timesheets and the real-time management of the electric fleet.

3.1.3 User requirements

This section contains tables that include the initial user requirements for the scenarios of this UC as described in the previous sections.

Table 4 - Requirements UC#1-RE-01

Field	Definition
ID	UC#1-RE-01
Title	Data ingestion from AMT ITSs to cloud
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC (function), DATA (data)
Description	Data are successfully transferred from AMT's Intelligent Transportation Systems to the project cloud
Additional information	N/A
Actor	AMT, ENG
Priority	MUST
Success Criteria	Successful completion of the first scenario
Expected delivery date	M36 (3 rd prototype)

Table 5 - Requirements UC#1-RE-02

Field	Definition
ID	UC#1-RE-02
Title	Data ingestion from cloud (external data) to cloud
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC (function), DATA (data)
Description	Data are successfully transferred from cloud (external data) to the project cloud
Additional information	N/A
Actor	AMT, ENG
Priority	MUST
Success Criteria	Successful completion of the first scenario
Expected delivery date	M36 (3 rd prototype)

Table 6 - Requirements UC#1-RE-03

Field	Definition
ID	UC#1-RE-03
Title	Data-enriched control panel for operation and maintenance
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC (function), DATA (data), ENV (Environmental)
Description	Management and control possibilities based on information enriched by data for improved operation and maintenance
Additional information	N/A
Actor	AMT, ENG
Priority	SHOULD
Success Criteria	Successful completion of the first scenario
Expected delivery date	M36 (3 rd prototype)

Table 7 - Requirements UC#1-RE-04

Field	Definition
ID	UC#1-RE-04
Title	Ability to perform analytics in the cloud on internal data
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC (function), DATA (data)
Description	Ability to analyse internal data in the shared cloud by applying artificial intelligence algorithms
Additional information	N/A
Actor	AMT, ENG
Priority	MUST
Success Criteria	Successful completion of the second scenario
Expected delivery date	M36 (3 rd prototype)

Table 8 - Requirements UC#1-RE-05

Field	Definition
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ID	UC#1-RE-05
Title	Possibility of enriching internal data analytics with external data (e.g. meteorological)
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC (function), DATA (data), ENV (Environmental)
Description	Ability to analyse internal data in the shared cloud by adding external data in order to enrich and improve the performance of applied algorithms
Additional information	N/A
Actor	AMT, ENG
Priority	SHOULD
Success Criteria	Successful completion of the second scenario
Expected delivery date	M36 (3 rd prototype)

Table 9 - Requirements UC#1-RE-06

Field	Definition
ID	UC#1-RE-06
Title	Overview of fleet data via dashboard
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC (function), DATA (data)
Description	Possibility to consult aggregated fleet data in an immediate and simplified manner
Additional information	N/A
Actor	AMT, ENG
Priority	MUST
Success Criteria	Successful completion of the third scenario
Expected delivery date	M36 (3 rd prototype)

Table 10 - Requirements UC#1-RE-07

Field	Definition
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ID	UC#1-RE-07
Title	Elaboration of average values and estimates of data needed for allocation (e.g. battery level)
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC (function), DATA (data), ENV (Environmental)
Description	Ability to consult statistically useful data obtained by processing available raw data and applying artificial intelligence algorithms
Additional information	N/A
Actor	AMT, ENG
Priority	MUST
Success Criteria	Successful completion of the third scenario
Expected delivery date	M36 (3 rd prototype)

Table 11 - Requirements UC#1-RE-08

Field	Definition
ID	UC#1-RE-08
Title	Display of alerts and suggestions
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC (function), DATA (data)
Description	Ability to display tips and alerts that can improve decision-making ability
Additional information	N/A
Actor	AMT, ENG
Priority	MAY
Success Criteria	Successful completion of the third scenario
Expected delivery date	M36 (3 rd prototype)

3.1.4 Description of datasets

This section contains tables that include descriptions of the datasets for the scenarios of this UC as described in the previous sections.

Table 12 - Dataset UC#1-DS-01

Field	Definition
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ID	UC#1-DS-01
Title	Group A
Description	It includes data about service execution and bus fleet (and GPS data)
Owner	AMT
Licence/Privacy	The data do not contain any information relevant to the privacy of individuals and are shared openly
Data type	Structured
Type of Process (Stream or Static data)	It depends on the specific data (see documentation for details)
Data Format	Mainly CSV, TXT, XLSX
Data Store	The data will be stored in the infrastructure made available to the project
Recommended API	-
Data Volume	Data is growing over time
Data Velocity	-
Documentation	A dedicated dataset description file is available
Data Origin	Data are collected within AMT's proprietary infrastructure
Will you reuse any existing data? If YES, which data and how?	Not currently
Methodologies for data collection/generation	AMT's proprietary infrastructure dedicated to automatic vehicle monitoring
Metadata and standards	See documentation for further details
For whom might the dataset be useful?	These data will be useful for all MOBISPACES stakeholders, e.g. product vendors, solution providers, solution integrators, policy makers, public transport users and public. Data can be used to verify infrastructure state and fleet immediate and future needs. In addition, it can be a starting point to develop systems tailored on own capabilities, criticalities and strengths, hence a way to improve performance in operation.
Data access, sharing and licensing	Data are freely available to MOBISPACES project participants and anyone else who explicitly requests them. Free sharing is permitted, industrial use is allowed with previous notification and subsequent consent by

	AMT.
Security needs/legal issues	AMT reserves the right to take legal action against industrial entities that use the data without prior notice and consent.
Class	Public

Table 13 - Dataset UC#1-DS-02

Field	Definition
ID	UC#1-DS-02
Title	Group B
Description	It includes data about bus fleet, vehicle scheduling, driver rostering, service planning/maintenance data, parking and dispatching.
Owner	AMT
Licence/Privacy	The data do not contain any information relevant to the privacy of individuals and are shared openly.
Data type	Structured
Type of Process (Stream or Static data)	It depends on the specific data (see documentation for details)
Data Format	Mainly CSV, TXT, XLSX
Data Store	The data will be stored in the infrastructure made available to the project.
Recommended API	-
Data Volume	Data is growing over time
Data Velocity	-
Documentation	A dedicated dataset description file is available
Data Origin	Data are collected within AMT's proprietary infrastructure
Will you reuse any existing data? If YES, which data and how?	Not currently
Methodologies for data collection/generation	AMT's proprietary infrastructure dedicated to automatic vehicle monitoring
Metadata and standards	See documentation for further details

For whom might the dataset be useful?	These data will be useful for all MOBISPACES stakeholders, e.g. product vendors, solution providers, solution integrators, policy makers, public transport users and public. Data can be used to verify infrastructure state and fleet immediate and future needs. In addition, it can be a starting point to develop systems tailored on own capabilities, criticalities and strengths, hence a way to improve performance in operation.
Data access, sharing and licensing	Data are freely available to MOBISPACES project participants and anyone else who explicitly requests them. Free sharing is permitted, industrial use is allowed with previous notification and subsequent consent by AMT.
Security needs/legal issues	AMT reserves the right to take legal action against industrial entities that use the data without prior notice and consent
Class	Public

Table 14 - Dataset UC#1-DS-03

Field	Definition
ID	UC#1-DS-03
Title	Group C
Description	It includes data about passengers (mobile application)
Owner	AMT
Licence/Privacy	The data do not contain any information relevant to the privacy of individuals and are shared openly.
Data type	Structured
Type of Process (Stream or Static data)	It depends on the specific data (see documentation for details)
Data Format	Mainly CSV, TXT, XLSX
Data Store	The data will be stored in the infrastructure made available to the project.
Recommended API	-
Data Volume	Data is growing over time
Data Velocity	-
Documentation	A dedicated dataset description file is available
Data Origin	Data are collected within AMT's proprietary infrastructure
Will you reuse any	Not currently

existing data? If YES, which data and how?	
Methodologies for data collection/generation	AMT's proprietary infrastructure dedicated to automatic vehicle monitoring and AMT's proprietary mobile application.
Metadata and standards	See documentation for further details
For whom might the dataset be useful?	These data will be useful for all MOBISPACES stakeholders, e.g. product vendors, solution providers, solution integrators, policy makers, public transport users and public. Data can be used to verify infrastructure state and fleet immediate and future needs. In addition, it can be a starting point to develop systems tailored on own capabilities, criticalities and strengths, hence a way to improve performance in operation.
Data access, sharing and licensing	Data are freely available to MOBISPACES project participants and anyone else who explicitly requests them. Free sharing is permitted, industrial use is allowed with previous notification and subsequent consent by AMT.
Security needs/legal issues	AMT reserves the right to take legal action against industrial entities that use the data without prior notice and consent
Class	Public

3.1.5 Current infrastructure

AMT manages public transport mobility services in the metropolitan area of Genova. A fleet of more than 950 buses, a metro line, two funiculars, 14 public lifts, a cog railway, a ferry boat and a country railway are used to satisfy the mobility needs of the citizens. About 100 buses are electric and all the new purchases will be so.

AMT bus fleet is managed through an AVM (Automated Vehicle Monitoring) System called "Simon". Simon consists of a Bus Control Centre, where the situation of the whole fleet is updated every 30 seconds, and one device per bus collects information from the bus and sends it to the centre. The device on the bus also allows reverse communication (from the centre to the bus). Some information, mainly regarding location, is sent in real time from the bus to the centre, and other information is sent at the end of the service when the bus comes back to the depot.

Two files are created every day by Simon: a file that contains all the information collected by the centre in real-time and a more detailed file that contains all the information sent by the bus at the end of the service. Both files are stored in AMT servers and can be made available to MOBISPACES partners daily.

To appreciate the real-time situation, Simon elaborates GTFS-Realtime, following Google Standards (Google Transit Feed Specification), allowing to know the current location and the

delay of every bus of the AMT fleet. This information is available at any moment (also for the MOBISPACES platform) through a password.

Information about bus systems, which also contain battery levels, is collected through the Canbus system. Canbus data are included in a file created at the end of the bus service, that is stored in AMT servers and can be made available to MOBISPACES partners daily. Currently, AMT does not have the possibility to verify battery levels in real-time. The efforts of the company are oriented to make these data available at any time as soon as possible.

This would strongly increase the excellence of the results of MOBISPACES UC #1.

3.2 UC#2 SmartSense - Intelligent Infrastructure Traffic Sensing (BOSCH)

3.2.1 Goals and objectives

All over Europe, cities are looking for concepts to reduce air pollution, with the efficient management of traffic still being a great challenge. Poor air quality is a major problem in urban areas, for whose improvement, reliable, extensive, and accurate data is needed, deriving mainly from smart sensing.

In 2021, WHO published a new air quality guideline reducing the limit values of air pollutants (e.g., NO₂ from 40yg/m³ to 10yg/m³), to eliminate the significant health effects of emissions in the EU and globally.

To get accurate data out of low-cost sensors, complex algorithms need to be developed to compensate for side effects. In addition to accurate air quality measurements, a detailed knowledge about traffic emissions as a main contributor to air quality and the dispersion of the emissions is needed.

In SmartSense, a system for monitoring and modelling the air quality in urban areas will be developed in Thessaloniki and used for efficient, environmentally sensitive traffic management.

BOSCH employs smart sensors in combination with emission and dispersion modelling to collect data that enable Environmental Sensitive Traffic Management following a closed-loop approach. This UC has as its main objective to offer the opportunity to prove the benefits and effectiveness of Environmental Sensitive Traffic Management based on accurate and reliable data.

Figure 7 - Environmental data driven traffic management

3.2.2 Description of scenarios

BOSCH delivers the following data regarding air emissions and air quality: traffic emissions, air quality measurements, air quality heatmaps.

Table 15 - Scenario UC#2-SCE-01

Field	Definition
ID	UC#2-SCE-01
Title	Traffic emissions
Description	Modelling of the traffic emissions to identify sections with high contributions to air quality. To introduce measures to reduce or limit emissions
Actors	Municipalities, traffic managers, traffic management companies, environmental offices, integrators
Objectives	Reduce traffic emissions
Pre-conditions	FCD raw data is available, traffic density and fleet composition is available Note: FCD means Floating Car Data with 1 Hz resolution
Process Description	Define designated area and covered road classes. Define used map material. Check availability and number of FCD raw data. Check availability of traffic models and define interfaces to get traffic volume. Set up an emission model. Set up an API to deliver the data.
Variations	Step 1-5 are mandatory, but this just reflects the base setup. In addition, further improvement for stability and additional influences can be developed.
Post-	Check the plausibility of generated data with established simple emission

conditions	models.
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Table 16 - Scenario UC#2-SCE-02

Field	Definition
ID	UC#2-SCE-02
Title	Local air quality measurements
Description	Set up local air quality measurement boxes in test area
Actors	Municipalities, traffic managers, traffic management companies, environmental offices, integrators
Objectives	Generate accurate and reliable air quality measurements from the test area for the most relevant locations
Pre-conditions	Test area is identified, stakeholders for installation are identified, air quality monitoring boxes are assembled
Process Description	Identify locations for installation. Check availability of 230V power supply and post to mount power supply. Deliver air quality monitoring boxes to the test area. Install air quality monitoring boxes and do electrical installation. Set up cloud instances and check on the first data. Set up an API to deliver the data.
Variations	-
Post-conditions	Regularly check plausibility of the data

Table 17 - Scenario UC#2-SCE-03

Field	Definition
ID	UC#2-SCE-03
Title	Air quality dispersion heatmap
Description	Generate air quality heatmap out of air quality measurements, weather data and emissions data
Actors	Municipalities, traffic managers, traffic management companies, environmental offices, integrators
Objectives	Generate air quality heatmap to analyse air quality at every location, get comprehensive understanding of influencing factors to digest the root causes of current heatmap
Pre-conditions	Traffic emission, air quality measurements, building data is available
Process	Get all the necessary input data for the designated area.

Description	Generate macroscopic numerical simulation to cover metrology. Generate microscopic dispersion simulation. Setup configuration for emission multiplication and data fusion with measurements. Setup API to deliver the data.
Variations	Calculation without emissions, calculation without air quality measurements
Post-conditions	Check plausibility of generated data

3.2.3 User requirements

This section contains tables that include the initial user requirements for the scenarios of this UC as described in the previous sections.

Table 18 - Requirements UC#2-RE-01

Field	Definition
ID	UC#2-RE-01
Title	Air quality measurements
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC (function), DATA (data)
Description	Expanded measurement accuracy for air quality measurements 25% NO ₂ , 50%% PM _x
Additional information	Meet requirements of indicative air quality category
Actor	Bosch team, environmental offices
Priority	MUST
Success Criteria	Collocation study with reference measurements
Expected delivery date	M24 (2 nd prototype)

Table 19 - Requirements UC#2-RE-02

Field	Definition
ID	UC#2-RE-02
Title	Emissions
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC (function), DATA (data)
Description	Generate area covering emission data for every hour

Additional information	For predefined road classes
Actor	Bosch team, environmental offices
Priority	MUST
Success Criteria	No gaps in data delivery
Expected delivery date	M24 (2 nd prototype)

Table 20 - Requirements UC#2-RE-03

Field	Definition
ID	UC#2-RE-03
Title	Heatmaps
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC (function), DATA (data)
Description	Validate measurements against defined estimated accuracy for each measurement location
Additional information	-
Actor	Bosch team
Priority	SHOULD
Success Criteria	Accuracy is within estimated range.
Expected delivery date	M24 (2 nd prototype)

Table 21 - Requirements UC#2-RE-04

Field	Definition
ID	UC#2-RE-04
Title	Emissions
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	PERF (Performance Requirements)
Description	Reduce traffic emissions by 20%
Additional information	Emissions at the beginning of the project
Actor	Bosch team, traffic managers, traffic management companies

Priority	MAY
Success Criteria	Comparison before and after implementation of environmental sensitive traffic management
Expected delivery date	M36 (3 rd prototype)

3.2.4 Description of datasets

This section contains tables that include descriptions of the datasets for the scenarios of this UC as described in the previous sections.

Table 22 - Dataset UC#2-DS-01

Field	Definition
ID	UC#2-DS-01
Title	Air quality measurements
Description	Time series hourly values NO2, PM2.5, PM10, O3 Notes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NO2 stands for Nitrogen Dioxide • PM2.5 stands for Particle mass average diameter < 2.5µm • PM10 stands for Particle mass average diameter < 10µm • O3 stands for Ozone
Owner	Bosch, data can be made publicly available
Licence/Privacy	Data can be imported to MOBISPACES platform
Data type	Structured
Type of Process (Stream or Static data)	Data stream of hourly air quality data
Data Format	CSV, JSON
Data Store	REST API
Recommended API	REST API
Data Volume	3 years data ~60GB
Data Velocity	-
Documentation	-
Data Origin	Data of installed air quality measurement boxes of test area in Thessaloniki
Will you reuse any existing data? If YES,	Air quality reference measurements for colocation study

which data and how?	
Methodologies for data collection/generation	Quantitative and qualitative measurement variables, etc.
Metadata and standards	IMEI, lat. / Ing. Notes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IMEI stands for International mobile equipment identity ● lat. stands for Latitude ● Ing. Stands for Longitude
For whom might the dataset be useful?	The outcomes dataset will be useful for all MOBISPACES stakeholders, including (for example) product vendors, solution providers, solution integrators, policy makers, students, researchers, academia, government and public organisations, urban authorities and municipalities, regulatory bodies.
Data access, sharing and licensing	Data can be made publicly available
Security needs/legal issues	-
Class	Public (PU)

Table 23 - Dataset UC#2-DS-02

Field	Definition
ID	UC#2-DS-02
Title	Traffic emissions
Description	Hourly NO2 data of traffic emissions in test area of Thessaloniki for defined road classes
Owner	Bosch
Licence/Privacy	Data can be imported to MOBISPACES platform
Data type	Structured
Type of Process (Stream or Static data)	Data stream traffic emissions data
Data Format	GeoJSON
Data Store	REST API
Recommended API	REST API

Data Volume	1 year's data ~100GB
Data Velocity	-
Documentation	-
Data Origin	Modelled data generated out of FCD raw data, traffic volume and fleet composition
Will you reuse any existing data? If YES, which data and how?	Traffic volume, statistical data for emission classes
Methodologies for data collection/generation	Modelled data
Metadata and standards	Link ID with reference to predefined map material
For whom might the dataset be useful?	The outcomes dataset will be useful for all MOBISPACES stakeholders, including (for example) product vendors, solution providers, solution integrators, policy makers, students, researchers, academia, government and public organisations, urban authorities and municipalities, regulatory bodies.
Data access, sharing and licensing	Data will be shared with the MOBISPACES platform
Security needs/legal issues	Standard access limitation with user and PW required
Class	Public (PU)

Table 24 - Dataset UC#2-DS-03

Field	Definition
ID	UC#2-DS-03
Title	Air quality heatmaps
Description	Hourly heatmaps of NO2, PM2.5 and PM10 of test area in Thessaloniki
Owner	Bosch
Licence/Privacy	Data can be imported to MOBISPACES platform
Data type	Structured
Type of Process (Stream or Static data)	Hourly updated heatmap
Data Format	Esri raster file

Data Store	REST API
Recommended API	REST API
Data Volume	1 year's data ~500GB
Data Velocity	-
Documentation	-
Data Origin	Modelled data out of weather, emissions, and air quality information
Will you reuse any existing data? If YES, which data and how?	Building data, traffic emissions, air quality measurements, weather data, land use and topographic information
Methodologies for data collection/generation	Modelled data
Metadata and standards	Lat. /lng. Data of simulated points with reference to upper left corner of defined test area
For whom might the dataset be useful?	The outcomes dataset will be useful for all MOBISPACES stakeholders, including (for example) product vendors, solution providers, solution integrators, policy makers, students, researchers, academia, government and public organisations, urban authorities and municipalities, regulatory bodies.
Data access, sharing and licensing	Data will be shared with the MOBISPACES platform
Security needs/legal issues	Standard access limitation with user and PW required
Class	Public (PU)

3.2.5 Current infrastructure

The Bosch Air Quality Solutions (AQS) infrastructure is designed to handle air quality measurement boxes, traffic and air quality simulations.

- The air quality measurement boxes are connected to the infrastructure as Internet of Things (IoT) devices, including device management, software maintenance and deployment on the devices, data management and data processing. Communication with other systems is handled by HTTP REST API as a general interface using established standards.
- The traffic data (using floating car data with a second-by-second resolution requiring the handling and storage of millions of data points per day) is managed within a Microsoft Azure-based cloud infrastructure, where in addition to the data enrichment with the time-resolved vehicle emissions, the localisation to the defined road network

elements, and the aggregation of the enriched traffic data to the road network is managed to provide an hourly heatmap which is accessible by HTTP REST API.

- The air quality dispersion modelling is implemented in Microsoft Azure batch to generate accurate hourly air quality heat maps based on the current environmental conditions, e.g., wind directions and wind speeds. KI/ML-based algorithms are used for data fusion of the emission sources and measured air quality values at certain points. The generated 2D heatmaps are accessible by HTTP REST API.

The defined Bosch AQS infrastructure encapsulates the specific tasks and provides standard interfaces for the data to other systems for ease of access.

3.3 UC#3 MT - Edge-powered Vessel Tracking (MT)

3.3.1 Goals and objectives

The Automatic Identification System (AIS) is a protocol based on VHF communication and it was established as an IMO standard in 2004. Since then, all commercial vessels over 299 gross Tonnage that travel internationally are obliged to carry AIS transponders. MarineTraffic owns the largest terrestrial network of AIS receivers worldwide, consisting of more than 5000 stations. The data collected from these receivers are complemented by third-party data collected by SAT-AIS providers (owning satellites with AIS receivers mounted on them). AIS data contain navigational information about vessels (e.g., location of a vessel, speed, course, etc.) as well as static information (identifier, flag, name, etc.). AIS is a collaborative system, as the crew of the vessel is responsible for transmitting AIS messages. As a result, the crew of a vessel might opt to switch off its AIS transponder for various reasons (e.g., to engage in illegal activities, escape sanctions, enter a piracy area, etc.) in order to avoid being tracked. These vessels are also known as “dark vessels”. In order to detect dark vessels, AIS needs to be combined with other data sources. Even if vessels have their transponder switched off, they have their radars on, for safety reasons. In this use case, the idea is to develop a new edge device that will collect both the radar transmissions of vessels and AIS messages. Fusing these two data sources will enable us to detect vessels that might have their AIS transponder switched-off.

The objective of this UC is to develop an edge-powered vessel tracker, named MT tracker, that will be able to combine two different kinds of vessel tracking data sources (AIS, X-Band, S-Band RF data) to increase the value of the original, by fusing data from collaborative vessel tracking sources (AIS) with non-collaborative sources (RF) using edge devices. In this way, users of vessel tracking services will have access to more accurate and richer vessel tracking data from multiple sources. By using edge devices, a big part of data processing will be performed in-situ, reducing the data and computational effort that needs to be pushed to centralised servers.

3.3.2 Description of scenarios

A UML diagram describing the actors of the use case and its core functions is provided in Figure 8. A vessel tracking provider (MarineTraffic) deploys the edge device and initiates an automatic workflow that runs on it, which receives AIS and RF data, preprocesses the data

and associates positions received from RF data to known AIS tracks (position-to-track). The fused tracks are then sent to a server, so that local tracks retrieved from edge devices are combined, producing global tracks. The global tracks and relevant analytics (e.g., statistics on dark targets), are visualised in a UI. Another actor, i.e., a customer of a vessel tracking data provider, interacts with this UI in order to retrieve information about vessel trajectories and statistics.

Figure 8 - UML Diagram for the MT Tracker UC

Table 25 - Scenario UC#3-SCE-01

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-SCE-01
Title	Ingestion and processing of AIS data on the edge device.
Description	The edge device should be equipped with an AIS receiver that will receive raw AIS messages. These messages will be processed in the edge device. The output of this service will be an AIS dataset with vessel tracking data ready to be consumed.
Actors	Vessel Tracking service provider, owner of the AIS network (MT) and the edge device.
Objectives	Ingest and process AIS data on the edge device.
Pre-conditions	AIS raw messages coming to the edge device, which is equipped with an AIS antenna.
Process Description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ingestion of streaming AIS raw messages. 2. Decoding. 3. Cleaning (e.g., removal of noise, outliers, in-land signals, etc.). 4. Output of processed, cleaned AIS messages.

Variations	Steps 1, 2, and 4 above are mandatory. Step 3 may include different sub-steps, depending on the quality of the input data.
Post-conditions	AIS processed messages in real-time

Table 26 - Scenario UC#3-SCE-02

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-SCE-02
Title	Ingestion and processing of RF data on the edge device.
Description	The edge device should be equipped with an RF receiver that will receive RF signals. These signals will be processed and converted on the edge device. The output of this service will be a dataset including the geo-referenced location of the detected targets.
Actors	Maritime intelligence provider (MT)
Objectives	Ingest and process RF data on the edge device
Pre-conditions	Two RF receivers should be operational on the edge device.
Process Description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ingestion of streaming RF signals 2. Signal-processing (e.g., conversion of RSSI to distance, georeferencing, etc.) 3. Cleaning (e.g., removal of noise) 4. Down-sampling (if necessary) 5. Cleaning (e.g., removal of noise) 6. Output of processed, cleaned RF messages
Variations	Step 4 might be optional
Post-conditions	Processed RF data, including the geo-referenced location of targets detected.

Table 27 - Scenario UC#3-SCE-03

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-SCE-03
Title	Data fusion of all vessel tracking sources (AIS, RF)
Description	Fuse processed AIS data with processed RF data to associate target positions of RF targets detected to AIS tracks. Processing should take place on the edge device. Unified tracks will result as output.
Actors	Maritime intelligence user
Objectives	Associate positions of targets detected in RF to AIS tracks.

Pre-conditions	Processed RF and AIS data available on the edge device
Process Description	Perform data fusion, taking as input the processed RF and AIS data available on the device. This process (position-to-track data fusion) should be
Variations	The data fusion position-to-track algorithm is not specified yet, and different approaches will be tested.
Post-conditions	Positions of detected targets via RF will be associated with AIS tracks.

Table 28 - Scenario UC#3-SCE-04

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-SCE-04
Title	Visualisation of all sources of vessel tracking data
Description	Vessel tracks coming from AIS and RF data sources, as well as statistics, are visualised in a web-based UI.
Actors	Maritime intelligence user
Objectives	Visualisation of vessel trajectories, dark vessels and statistics
Pre-conditions	Result of data fusion: AIS data fused with RF data
Process Description	Vessel positions coming from AIS and RF streams will be displayed on a web-based map. Information about vessels will be displayed (e.g., speed, vessel type, etc.) if the user clicks on a vessel position. "Dark vessels" will also be displayed. These are vessels that have their AIS transponder off, but they can be tracked using RF data. Statistics about vessels (e.g, percentage of dark vessels in area) will also be displayed.
Variations	N/A
Post-conditions	Visualisation of vessels and statistics

Table 29 - Scenario UC#3-SCE-05

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-SCE-05
Title	Semantic enrichment of vessel tracking data
Description	Vessel tracking data will be fused with linked open data in order to be enriched with arbitrary information, e.g., information about the ports/marinas that the vessels are located at.
Actors	Maritime intelligence user

Objectives	Semantic enrichment of vessel tracking data with linked open data
Pre-conditions	Streams of vessel trajectories
Process Description	A stream of vessel trajectories will be the input of this process, which will be the output of UC#3-SCE-04. These trajectories will consist of AIS and RF vessel positions. These real-time streams of data will be fused/interlinked with linked open data sources providing information about ports/marinas.
Variations	N/A
Post-conditions	Vessel trajectories enriched with data about ports/marinas that the vessels reside in.

3.3.3 User requirements

This section contains tables that include the initial user requirements for the scenarios of this UC as described in the previous sections.

Table 30 - Requirements UC#3-RE-01

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-RE-01
Title	Real-time AIS data ingestion on the edge device
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC
Description	The edge device should be equipped with an operational AIS receiver so that raw AIS messages can be ingested.
Additional information	N/A
Actor	Vessel tracking data provider
Priority	MAN
Success Criteria	Operational AIS receiver mounted on the edge device
Expected delivery date	M12 (1 st prototype)

Table 31 - Requirements UC#3-RE-02

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-RE-02
Title	Real-time AIS processing on the edge device
Level of detail	Stakeholder

Type	FUNC, PERF
Description	AIS data received through the AIS receiver mounted on the edge device will need to be processed (decoded, transformed, cleaned, timestamped, etc.) in real-time
Additional information	N/A
Actor	Vessel tracking data provider
Priority	MAN
Success Criteria	Pre-processed AIS dataset available on-the edge device in real-time
Expected delivery date	M12 (1 st prototype)

Table 32 - Requirements UC#3-RE-03

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-RE-03
Title	Data cleaning for AIS data
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC
Description	AIS data, after being pre-processed, should be cleaned, removing noise (erroneous attributes).
Additional information	N/A
Actor	Maritime intelligence provider
Priority	MAN
Success Criteria	AIS data with no missing values and no outliers
Expected delivery date	M12 (1 st prototype)

Table 33 - Requirements UC#3-RE-04

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-RE-04
Title	Real-time RF data ingestion on the edge device
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC

Description	Two edge devices will be constructed, each one having an AIS receiver and an RF front-end.
Additional information	N/A
Actor	Maritime intelligence provider
Priority	MAN
Success Criteria	Two operational RF front ends mounted on edge devices, receiving RF signals. Raw data should be available in the device(s).
Expected delivery date	M12 (1 st prototype)

Table 34 - Requirements UC#3-RE-05

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-RE-05
Title	RF data processing on edge
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC, PERF
Description	Received RF signals should be converted to meaningful data using a processing chain that includes cleaning, RSSI-to-distance conversion, timestamping, and (if needed) down-sampling. The process should be automated, deployed on the edge device, and deliver results in real-time.
Additional information	N/A
Actor	Maritime intelligence provider
Priority	MAN
Success Criteria	For each RF source, a dataset with geo-referenced detected targets should be available, along with the timestamp of acquisition, in real-time
Expected delivery date	M12 (1 st prototype)

Table 35 - Requirements UC#3-RE-06

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-RE-06
Title	Position-to-track association on edge in real-time

Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC, PERF
Description	Associate RF detected positions to AIS tracks in real-time. Processing should take place on the edge device and accuracy should be > 85%.
Additional information	N/A
Actor	Maritime intelligence provider
Priority	MAN
Success Criteria	For each RF source, a dataset with geo-referenced detected targets and associated AIS tracks should be available, along with the timestamp of acquisition. Position-to-track operation should deliver results in real-time and achieve > 85% in accuracy.
Expected delivery date	M12 (1 st prototype)

Table 36 - Requirements UC#3-RE-07

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-RE-07
Title	Track-to-track association on edge in real-time
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC, PERF
Description	Associate tracks collected from the output of position-to-track association performed in each edge device. Produce global tracks with accuracy > 80%.
Additional information	N/A
Actor	Maritime intelligence provider
Priority	MAN
Success Criteria	Track-to-track algorithm should be performed in real-time and achieve > 80% in accuracy.
Expected delivery date	M12 (1 st prototype)

Table 37 - Requirements UC#3-RE-08

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-RE-08

Title	Visualisation of vessel tracking data coming from different sources, associated tracks on the map and statistics
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC
Description	Visualisation of vessel tracking data coming from different sources, associated tracks on the map and statistics. Also, visualisation of enriched information using semantic web technologies (e.g., information about the ports/marinas near which the detected vessels are located).
Additional information	N/A
Actor	Maritime intelligence user
Priority	DES
Success Criteria	Web-based UI displaying the following information (minimum): Positions received from RF data, AIS data, unified tracks, and statistics (number of tracks and positions associated, number of not associated positions (dark vessels), etc. All geographical data should be displayed on the map and statistics should be displayed in the form of dashboards.
Expected delivery date	M12 (1 st prototype)

Table 38 - Requirements UC#3-RE-09

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-RE-09
Title	Semantic modelling of maritime data and semantic data fusion with arbitrary open data
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC
Description	<p>Semantically enrich the AIS/RF global trajectories (i.e., the output of the track-to-track operation) with arbitrary information existing in open data endpoints (e.g., ports/marinas close to which the vessels are located). More specifically, the following steps should be performed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The streams of global tracks from AIS and RF are received as input • The data get transformed into RDF • The data get combined with data from endpoints containing arbitrary information (e.g., ports/marinas) based on spatial relationships that hold between the entities involved (e.g., vessels located in ports). Data fusion can be done either using interlinking or federation.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Since this is a real-time use case and the input data are coming in streaming fashion, the whole processing chain described above should be done in near real-time, so streaming/online technologies should be used.
Additional information	N/A
Actor	Maritime intelligence user
Priority	MAN
Success Criteria	Online transformation of vessel tracking data into RDF and interlinking/federation with other open data to retrieve arbitrary information (e.g., ports/marinas) in near real-time.
Expected delivery date	M24 (2 nd prototype)

3.3.4 Dataset requirements

This section contains tables that include descriptions of the datasets for the scenarios of this UC as described in the previous sections.

Table 39 - Dataset UC#3-DS-01

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-DS-01
Title	AIS dataset
Description	This an AIS dataset that will be produced by the data collected from the AIS receiver mounted on the edge device. The dataset will contain navigational information about the movement of vessels in vicinity (e.g., coordinates, course, heading, speed etc.) as well as static information (e.g., vessel type, identifier).
Owner	The AIS receiver which will be used in this UC is part of the AIS terrestrial network owned by MarineTraffic. Access to anonymised data will be granted to the members of the consortium.
Licence/Privacy	MarineTraffic AIS data will stay on MT premises, however, part of the anonymised AIS dataset will be shared with the consortium.
Data type	Processed AIS data are structured.
Type of Process (Stream or Static data)	Both stream and static data.
Data Format	There is flexibility regarding the format. We can make the data available as .csv files, but other options can be accommodated. This needs to be specified later in the project.

Data Store	Currently, we store them in relational databases and the datasets are also available as Kafka topics. But none of these options are currently operational on the edge device. This will be specified in the future.
Recommended API	REST API is our preferred option
Data Volume	Since this is a real-time UC that will use primarily streaming data, volume is not very relevant. It depends on the retention period that we will specify (not specified yet).
Data Velocity	200KB /min (estimated velocity on the edge device)
Documentation	MarineTraffic sample AIS dataset available online: https://zenodo.org/record/3754481#.Y0IOjyORo8Q
Data Origin	AIS data for UC3 will be collected using MT AIS receivers mounted on the edge devices.
Will you reuse any existing data? If YES, which data and how?	Raw data will be collected from the AIS antenna mounted on the edge device and will be decoded and pre-processed.
Methodologies for data collection/generation	Described in the UC/requirements sections.
Metadata and standards	No metadata foreseen at this point.
For whom might the dataset be useful?	Users of vessel tracking services, such as: vessel traffic officers, mariners, maritime data scientists, analysts on the maritime domain, insurance companies, shipping companies, naval deference agencies, etc.
Data access, sharing and licensing	Samples of anonymized data will be available internally to the consortium members.
Security needs/legal issues	Data will be anonymized
Class	Internal

Table 40 - Dataset UC#3-DS-02

Field	Definition
ID	UC#3-DS-02
Title	RF data
Description	Data coming from X-Band and S-Band receivers mounted on the edge device(s).
Owner	MarineTraffic owns the data.

Licence/Privacy	The data will stay on premise because the biggest part of the processing chain of this use case must take place on the edge device. However, part of the data will be shared with the consortium.
Data type	Structured
Type of Process (Stream or Static data)	Stream data primarily (static samples will also be used for testing)
Data Format	Not specified yet
Data Store	No data store used at present
Recommended API	Redis
Data Volume	Data Volume = Data Velocity * Data Retention. Assuming a retention of 1 day the volume would be approximately 1.5 GB/day.
Data Velocity	1.1MB /min (estimation)
Documentation	Not available yet
Data Origin	A board including RF receivers that will be developed in the project.
Will you reuse any existing data? If YES, which data and how?	Data will be collected from scratch.
Methodologies for data collection/generation	Described in previous sections (UC description/requirements)
Metadata and standards	No metadata foreseen now
For whom might the dataset be useful?	Users of vessel tracking services, such as: vessel traffic officers, mariners, maritime data scientists, analysts on the maritime domain, insurance companies, shipping companies, naval defence agencies, etc. (same as AIS data).
Data access, sharing and licensing	The dataset will be made available to the project partners, but it will not be shared publicly
Security needs/legal issues	The data will be anonymised
Class	Internal

3.3.5 Current infrastructure

MarineTraffic owns the world's largest proprietary AIS network, consisting of over 5,000 coastal AIS stations worldwide. In this way, MarineTraffic is tracking over 200,000 vessels in real time. With its Big Data infrastructure, MarineTraffic receives hundreds of millions of

vessel positions daily and archives billions of records. In the context of the MT Tracker pilot, MarineTraffic AIS data will be used. In the context of MOBISPACES, we are developing new edge devices that will include an AIS receiver mounted, along with an RF front-end which will receive RF transmissions from vessels, and a computational unit (i.e., NVIDIA Orin) which will be used to perform data processing and ML tasks on the edge devices. These devices will be deployed in coastal areas in the same way that existing MarineTraffic terrestrial AIS receivers are installed. The results of the edge computing tasks will be forwarded to a server located at the MarineTraffic premises. The edge devices will not be accessible directly to the consortium members, but the components developed in MOBISPACES for this use case will be deployed on the edge devices and the server by the MarineTraffic MOBISPACES team.

3.4 UC#4 VesselEdge - Edge Computing Onboard of Moving Vessels (FRQ)

3.4.1 Goals and objectives

The goal of this UC is to validate that collecting and processing onboard data vessels with limited connectivity can be accomplished and provide a way to improve situational awareness by overcoming the limitation of geographical coverage of coastal AIS and lack of high-speed communication networks at sea.

The main objective is to deploy a smart pre-processing AIS system (“VesselEdge”) on vessels which will serve as a mobile sensor. This will enable efficient data operations between vessels and a control room.

Figure 9 - Sample view of operator visualisation without / with VesselEdge

The objective is to extend the AIS coverage beyond the reach of coastal AIS antennas (or in areas with limited or temporarily not available coverage) by deploying the above-mentioned vessels at sea to extend situational awareness for the operator in the control room.

Thus, the KPIs for the use case are:

- successful deployment of a novel smart AIS system that pre-processes the raw AIS data stream and transmits the key information (local model) back to the control room (target: deployments on 3 ships, baseline: current vessel AIS systems are only used for on-board situation awareness)
- extended AIS coverage beyond the reach of coastal AIS antennas (target: extend AIS coverage on-demand by linking sensors onboard of moving vessels, baseline: current terrestrial AIS coverage at the use case location)

The smart pre-processing AIS will reduce the raw information to key information (local model) to be transferred back to the control room, where multiple local models will be recovered for an overall situation awareness of the control room (coastal hub).

The following figures provide the goal for data transfer.

Table 41 - SAT-AIS as baseline comparison

KPI	Actual Value	Goal	Gain
Data Rate	38.4 kbit/s	3...32 kbit/s	5...10
Latency	3...4 h	< 5s	1000

As an additional objective, the possibility to share local models of one control room (coastal hub) between control rooms (coastal hubs) from possible different organisational/legal entities (without sharing the raw data) for an improved overall situational awareness of a bigger area can be exploited.

Further, the UC can be used to exploit the advantage of other MOBISPACES outcomes set in place, to enrich the information with other data (weather, tidal, hydrographic, ...).

3.4.2 Description of scenarios

Frequentis (FRQ) will work with one of its customers to prepare and deploy vessels to achieve the objectives of this UC.

Figure 10 presents planned AIS data process flow from Vessel (Far Edge) to Control Room (Near Edge) visualisation including planned interfacing for UC#4-SCE-01 (US4_001).

Figure 10 - UC#4-SCE-01 (US4_001, US4_002) Extend Situational Awareness Use Case flow

Table 42 - Scenario UC#4-SCE-01

Field	Definition
ID	UC#4-SCE-01
Title	Extend Situational Awareness
Description	A maritime control room needs to extend its situation awareness by deploying a mobile sensor (“VesselEdge”) to the position of interest.
Actors	Vessel (e.g., Rescue Vessel) with “VesselEdge”, Neighbouring Vessels at Scene, Control Room, Operator/Rescue Mission Coordinator
Objectives	To provide situational awareness to the control room operator where he otherwise would have “a blank spot”, by providing data for visualisation of situation on the scene of the deployed Vessel.
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● VesselEdge prepared: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Smart-AIS-pre-processing Edge device (“VesselEdge”) is deployed at vessel ○ AIS raw messages coming to the edge device ○ Communication link available to control room ○ Control room is equipped with data processing system to receive & process data from Vessel ● Situational-awareness is needed at a “blank spot”

	<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 11 - No situational awareness due to no AIS-coverage</p>
<p>Process Description</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Incident happened and is reported to Control room at a location without AIS coverage 2. Operator/"Rescue Mission Coordinator" deploys Rescue vessel which has smart-AIS-pre-processing Edge device ("VesselEdge") on board 3. AIS receiver of the Vessel deployed receives AIS information (position, vessel information) from neighbour vessels 4. Anomaly detection and prioritisation processes (ML-based) are run on smart-AIS-pre-processing Edge device ("VesselEdge") 5. AIS information is pre-processed on the vessel and only key information (local model) is transferred to the control room as per set prioritisation. 6. Control room processes key-information (recovers model) and visualise neighbour vessels (situation picture) for the Operator/"Rescue Mission Coordinator"
<p>Variations</p>	<p>Instead of an incident triggering this process the following could be envisioned:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Event (e.g., yacht race) is happening in an area with-out coastal AIS Coverage ● Defect / Maintenance of part of coastal AIS Coverage
<p>Post-conditions</p>	<p>Situational Awareness is available:</p>

Figure 12 - Situation awareness due to Vessel Edge

In Case of a maritime agency would like to collaborate with its neighbouring maritime agency/ies by sharing collected data via VesselEdge (AIS data), this collaboration helps to improve learning in the entire area. Figure 11 presents – when data sharing allowed – planned flow between processes units of Control Room (Near Edge – source) and Other Control Room (Near Edge – neighbouring) via Cloud environment for UC#4-SCE-02.

Figure 13 - UC#4-SCE-02 (US4_002) Sharing Between Organizations UC

Table 43 - Scenario UC#4-SCE-02

Field	Definition
ID	UC#4-SCE-02
Title	Sharing Between Organizations
Description	A maritime agency would like to collaborate with its neighbouring maritime agency by sharing data (AIS data), without sharing the raw full AIS data but the learnings from within to improve learning in the entire area.
Actors	Maritime Agencies (VTS operators) Maritime Agencies (VTS operators)
Objectives	To share “behaviour learnings” from raw data with other entities without sharing the raw data.

Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Smart-AIS-pre-processing Edge device is deployed at vessel ● AIS raw messages coming to the edge device ● Communication link available to control room ● Control rooms are equipped with a data processing system to process received aggregated data from Vessel and reconstruct trajectory. ● Cloud environments are available to share, process data from local systems.
Process Description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. VesselEdge and Coastal receiver collect AIS information 2. Local system is processing AIS information for improved local situation awareness 3. Findings (e.g., “behaviour”, “patterns”) are shared regularly / automatically to the cloud & combined and processed there. 4. Other systems may consume & contribute to this shared information.
Variations	N/A
Post-conditions	Situation awareness improvement from AIS data can be achieved for an area regardless of if multiple different agencies/entities are the source of the raw data.

3.4.3 User requirements

This section contains tables that include the initial user requirements for the scenarios of this UC as described in the previous sections.

Table 44 - Requirements UC#4-RE-01

Field	Definition
ID	UC#4-RE-01
Title	Real-time AIS data ingestion on the edge device
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC
Description	The edge device should be equipped with an operational AIS receiver so that raw AIS messages can be ingested.
Additional information	User story: I want to have visibility of the situation on scene even if I do not have AIS coverage for the place of incident
Actor	Vessel tracking data provider
Priority	MUST
Success Criteria	Operational AIS receiver mounted on the edge device with access to AIS data (simulated or real)
Expected delivery date	M36

Table 45 - Requirements UC#4-RE-02

Field	Definition
ID	UC#4-RE-02
Title	Real-time AIS processing on the edge device
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC, PERF
Description	AIS data received through the AIS receiver mounted on the edge device will need to be processed (decoded, transformed, cleaned, timestamped, etc.) in real-time
Additional information	Will be provided as part of the UC implementation User story: I want to have visibility of the situation on scene even if I do not have AIS coverage for the place of incident
Actor	FRQ
Priority	MUST
Success Criteria	Pre-processed AIS dataset available on-the edge device in real-time
Expected delivery date	M36

Table 46 - Requirements UC#4-RE-03

Field	Definition
ID	UC#4-RE-03
Title	"Data reduction" on the edge device
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC, PERF
Description	1.approach: trajectory compression (for visualisation purposes) 2.approach: federated learning (for anomaly detection purposes) Previously cleaned AIS data is reduced on the edge device in order to reduce the data size for transmission to shore.
Additional information	Subject of the UC implementation User story: I want to have visibility of the situation on scene even if I do not have AIS coverage for the place of incident
Actor	AIT/ULB
Priority	MUST
Success Criteria	Locally trained anomaly detection model and compressed trajectories (in order to reduce amount of data transmitted).

	Dataset needs to be smaller to account for limited bandwidth
Expected delivery date	M36

Table 47 - Requirements UC#4-RE-04

Field	Definition
ID	UC#4-RE-04
Title	Communication while Vessel is at sea
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC
Description	A communication platform is required, enabling communication even while the vessel is at sea.
Additional information	For the use-case a global connectivity is not required as the tests will mainly be carried within range of mobile connectivity
Actor	FRQ
Priority	MUST
Success Criteria	Data communication is available, in 2 directions (ship to coast and coast to ship)
Expected delivery date	M36

Table 48 - Requirements UC#4-RE-05

Field	Definition
ID	UC#4-RE-05
Title	Visualisation of data coming from “VesselEdge” Devices
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC
Description	Within the Control Room, data received from the VesselEdge Devices shall be visualised on a chart which is used to present situational awareness to the Operator 1.approach: visualisation of trajectories for enhanced situational awareness 2.approach: visualisation of detected anomalies
Additional information	User story: I want to have visibility of the situation on scene even if I do not have AIS coverage for the place of incident
Actor	FRQ

Priority	MUST
Success Criteria	User Interface (Chart) which is extended by situational awareness gained from "VesselEdge".
Expected delivery date	M36

Table 49 - Requirements UC#4-RE-06

Field	Definition
ID	UC#4-RE-06
Title	Vessels and area for testing available
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	ENV
Description	For the UC vessels and an area for testing shall be available
Additional information	User story: I want to have visibility of the situation on scene even if I do not have AIS coverage for the place of incident
Actor	FRQ, Vessel
Priority	MUST
Success Criteria	Vessel and Area available for UC
Expected delivery date	M36

Table 50 - Requirements UC#4-RE-07

Field	Definition
ID	UC#4-RE-07
Title	Container Environment on Edge Device
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	ENV
Description	For the processing on the vessel a docker container environment on an edge device shall be available
Additional information	User story: I want to have visibility of the situation on scene even if I do not have AIS coverage for the place of incident
Actor	FRQ
Priority	MUST
Success Criteria	Container environment ready for container deployment

Expected delivery date	M36 (Mid-term review planned)
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Table 51 - Requirements UC#4-RE-08

Field	Definition
ID	UC#4-RE-08
Title	Real-time AIS data ingestion on shore
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC
Description	Compressed trajectory data to be reconstructed for visualisation in real-time
Additional information	User story: Maritime agency want to be able to share "behavioural learning" from their area with other neighbouring agencies without sharing the actual AIS data (and vice-versa)
Actor	FRQ
Priority	SHOULD
Success Criteria	Trajectory data ready for visualisation
Expected delivery date	M36

Table 52 - Requirements UC#4-RE-09

Field	Definition
ID	UC#4-RE-09
Title	Real-time AIS processing on shore
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC, PERF
Description	Reconstructed trajectories from UC#4-RE-08 to train an anomaly detection
Additional information	User story: Maritime agency want to be able to share "behavioural learning" from their area with other neighbouring agencies without sharing the actual AIS data (and vice-versa)
Actor	AIT
Priority	SHOULD
Success Criteria	Trained (anomaly detection) model available.
Expected delivery date	M36

Table 53 - Requirements UC#4-RE-10

Field	Definition
ID	UC#4-RE-10
Title	federated learning
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC, PERF
Description	Processable AIS data shall be reduced to key information (local model/anomalies)
Additional information	User story: Maritime agency want to be able to share "behavioural learning" from their area with other neighbouring agencies without sharing the actual AIS data (and vice-versa)
Actor	AIT
Priority	SHOULD
Success Criteria	Local models can be shared between organisation
Expected delivery date	M36

Table 54 - Requirements UC#4-RE-11

Field	Definition
ID	UC#4-RE-11
Title	Data format for sharing learnings (anomaly detection) with other agencies
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	ENV
Description	Data format for sharing learnings (anomaly detection) with other agencies
Additional information	User story: Maritime agency want to be able to share "behavioural learning" from their area with other neighbouring agencies without sharing the actual AIS data (and vice-versa)
Actor	AIT, FRQ
Priority	SHOULD
Success Criteria	Documentation for data format available
Expected delivery date	M36

3.4.4 Description of datasets

This section contains tables that include descriptions of the datasets for the scenarios of this UC as described in the previous sections.

Table 55 - Dataset UC#4-DS-01

Field	Definition
ID	UC#4-DS-01
Title	AIS kinematic dataset
Description	AIS position updates collected while testing UC
Owner	Third party supporting UC (Vessel Operator)
Licence/Privacy	The AIS data will stay on premise (on the Vessel) as the use-case is about not transferring the raw data. Historical example raw data though can be provided to members of the consortium.
Data type	Processed AIS data are structured.
Type of Process (Stream or Static data)	Stream
Data Format	NMEA stream
Data Store	The data is not intended and not required to be stored for the use-case but processed as a stream.
Recommended API	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● OPT1: JSON/ws (towards an available NMEA Decoder & Tracker) ● OPT2: Alternatively for cleaning for raw data NMEA serial stream access
Data Volume	Since this is a real-time use case that will use primarily streaming data, volume is not very relevant. Kinematic data with approximately 10 features.
Data Velocity	0.5 updates per second per vessel
Documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● JSON over websockets, details will be provided on request (OPT1); ● AIS Data format: ITU-R M.1371 (OPT2); ● Encapsulation format: Electronics Association NMEA 0183 Standard for Interfacing Marine Electronic Devices Version 4.00 November 1, 2008 (OPT2)
Data Origin	AIS data for UC4 will be collected using AIS receivers mounted on the edge devices. Frequentis will provide processing (NMEA decoder & tracker) and processed interface (JSON/ws) for easier integration of other components at Edge.
Will you reuse any existing data? If YES,	Raw data will be collected from the AIS antenna mounted on the edge device and will be decoded and pre-processed.

which data and how?	
Methodologies for data collection/generation	Described in the UC/requirements sections.
Metadata and standards	No metadata foreseen at this point.
For whom might the dataset be useful?	For other MOBISPACES partners providing edge computing applications, etc. to perform required processing for the UC.
Data access, sharing and licensing	N/A as data will only be on Vessel. Examples of AIS data can be provided.
Security needs/legal issues	N/A (AIS Data)
Class	Internal

3.4.5 Current infrastructure

Use Case visualised by overlaying reference architecture on the actual operational environment of Maritime Agencies [SAR (Search and Rescue) / GMDSS (Global Maritime Distress and Safety System) / VTS (Vessel traffic services) / CSS (Coastal Surveillance System)] in Figure 12.

Figure 14 - Use Case overview

The use-case will be performed on the Edge meaning:

- The “Far” Edge consists of the device for smart pre-processing AIS system (“VesselEdge”) on board the moving vessel
- The “Near” Edge consists of a Server located at the Coastal Control Room (virtualized private IT infrastructure/data centre)

For this Edge infrastructure, the environment of a Frequentis Customer will be used, which consists of the following:

- Vessels, incl. its Sensors (AIS receiver)
- Vessel-to-shore communication means (or simulated) & other network infrastructure
- Coastal Control Room Infrastructure (Privately hosted Server, virtual IT Infrastructure)

The far-edge device will be built for this use-case & deployed on a vessel, connecting to the AIS sensor and communication equipment. A raspberry Pi4 or Intel NUC is planned. In all cases robust for operation at sea/vessel. A container environment also on the far edge device is envisioned.

For the UC the communication channel/data link will be simulating:

Table 56 - UC#4 communication channel/data link information

Data Link	Data Rate	Coverage
Satellite	32 ... 128 kbit/s	globally
VDES	310 kbit/s	30 nmi
HF/MF data link	< 5 kbit/s	300 nmi

For the near-edge components (software components only), a container (docker) environment will be available/prepared.

Access to this Production Edge environment is only possible via Frequentis. However, a test/simulation environment is available.

The cloud is not part of the main objective, but the second scenario described above. Any commonly used cloud environment (e.g., AWS) is suitable.

The following figure provides an overview of the envisioned deployment:

Figure 15 - Planned deployment diagram

3.5 UC#5 CrowdSeaMapping - Federated Learning for Enhancing Nautical Charts (GST)

3.5.1 Goals and objectives

The goal of this UC is to validate that collecting and processing Crowdsourced Bathymetric data (CSB) onboard vessels with limited processing capabilities and connectivity can be accomplished and provide a platform collecting, processing, and evaluating data decentrally on the edge devices.

3.5.2 Description of scenarios

Table 57 - Scenario UC#5-SCE-01

Field	Definition
ID	UC#5-SCE-01
Title	Real time detection and reporting on unexpected low depths
Description	The edge devices should be able to process collected CSB data in real time and determine if depths lower than expected are observed. Such information, indicating that existing depth models may be imprecise, can be crucial for safety. The mariner should be noticed and observation be communicated to the hydrographic office.
Actors	Vessel, Hydrographic Office
Objectives	Ingest and process GNSS and depth sensor data on the edge device and evaluate these using trained machine learning model.
Pre-conditions	GNSS and depth sensor information available. Machine learning model trained.
Process Description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ingest GNSS and depth sensor data 2. Fusion sensor data into CSB data 3. Evaluate sensor data using machine learning model 4. Warn mariner on unexpected reduced depths 5. Store and communicate finding with hydrographic office
Variations	Step 4 can be omitted, often internal echo sounder systems already provide real-time feedback to mariners.
Post-conditions	Streaming available fused GNSS and depth sensor, information about areas with potential hazards to navigation.

Table 58 - Scenario UC#5-SCE-02

Field	Definition
ID	UC#5-SCE-02
Title	Quality assessment of existing depth model

Description	Existing depth models are created from a wide variety of data, including historic data being up to 150 years old. Evaluating existing depth model with CSB data enables surveyors to help identify where efforts can be put into resurveying.
Actors	Vessel, Hydrographic Office, surveyor
Objectives	Evaluate larger areas of depth model to assess quality
Pre-conditions	CSB data, i.e. fused GNSS and depth sensor data
Process Description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Evaluate CSB sensor data using a machine learning model. 2. Inform hydrographic office about quality assessment of depth model, if low data communication only inform about areas of low quality.
Variations	Step 1 can also be evaluated centrally at centralised infrastructure, requiring all CSB data to be transferred to centralised server.
Post-conditions	A quality measure of the existing depth model.

Table 59 - Scenario UC#5-SCE-03

Field	Definition
ID	UC#5-SCE-03
Title	Improved coverage of depth model
Description	When CSB data is collected in areas with missing data it should be evaluated if CSB data can provide valuable contributions to existing depth model.
Actors	Vessel, Hydrographic Office
Objectives	Contribute to depth model with CSB data where depth model is missing data.
Pre-conditions	CSB data, i.e. fused GNSS and depth sensor data
Process Description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Evaluate CSB sensor data using machine learning model to identify if CSB data can contribute to depth model. 2. Train local machine learning model with CSB data in areas with missing data. 3. Share updated machine learning model with centralised backend
Variations	Instead of step 2-3 CSB data can also be shared directly with a centralised server which can update the central machine learning model.
Post-conditions	A depth model contributed with collected CSB data where the depth model is lacking data.

3.5.3 User requirements

This section contains tables that include the initial user requirements for the scenarios of this UC as described in the previous sections.

Table 60 - Requirements UC#5-RE-01

Field	Definition
ID	UC#5-RE-01
Title	Real time GNSS sensor data ingestion on the edge device
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	DATA
Description	GNSS sensor data can be collected from vessels and ingested to edge devices in real time.
Additional information	-
Actor	GST
Priority	Must
Success Criteria	Edge device can receive real time GNSS sensor data from vessel
Expected delivery date	M24

Table 61 - Requirements UC#5-RE-02

Field	Definition
ID	UC#5-RE-02
Title	Real time depth sensor data ingestion on the edge device
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	DATA
Description	Depth sensor data can be collected from a vessel's echo sounder and ingested to edge devices in real time.
Additional information	-
Actor	GST
Priority	Must
Success Criteria	Edge device can receive real time depth sensor data from vessel
Expected delivery date	M24

Table 62 - Requirements UC#5-RE-03

Field	Definition
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ID	UC#5-RE-03
Title	Real time data evaluation using machine learning model on edge device
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC, PERF
Description	The edge device should be able to evaluate incoming sensor data in real time using a machine learning model.
Additional information	-
Actor	GST
Priority	Must
Success Criteria	The edge device is able to keep up with the stream of incoming data.
Expected delivery date	M36

Table 63 - Requirements UC#5-RE-04

Field	Definition
ID	UC#5-RE-04
Title	Visualise machine learning sensor evaluation output
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC
Description	Evaluated sensor data should be visualised and presented in a graphical way to enable easy interpretation of machine learning model output.
Additional information	-
Actor	GST, Mariner
Priority	May
Success Criteria	An easy interpretable overview of the evaluation of the CSB data, showing whether any dangers to navigation are present.
Expected delivery date	M24

Table 64 - Requirements UC#5-RE-05

Field	Definition
ID	UC#5-RE-05

Title	CSB data available for edge device
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	DATA
Description	A CSB data set should be available as data foundation. This is generated from fused GNSS and depth sensor data.
Additional information	-
Actor	GST
Priority	Must
Success Criteria	Edge device can receive real time GNSS sensor data from vessel
Expected delivery date	M36

Table 65 - Requirements UC#5-RE-06

Field	Definition
ID	UC#5-RE-06
Title	CSB data evaluation using machine learning model
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC, PERF
Description	Machine learning models should be able to evaluate CSB faster than data is ingested.
Additional information	-
Actor	GST
Priority	Must
Success Criteria	Edge device can receive real time GNSS sensor data from vessel
Expected delivery date	M36

Table 66 - Requirements UC#5-RE-07

Field	Definition
ID	UC#5-RE-07
Title	A communication platform is required, enabling communication even while vessel is at sea

Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC
Description	A communication platform is necessary for being able to communicate from vessels to a centralised model, even while at sea. This is necessary to be able to provide feedback to centralised models on machine learning findings.
Additional information	-
Actor	GST
Priority	Should
Success Criteria	
Expected delivery date	M36

Table 67 - Requirements UC#5-RE-08

Field	Definition
ID	UC#5-RE-08
Title	Update federated machine learning model with CSB data
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC
Description	When the edge device machine learning model has been updated with improved findings, this information should be federated back to the centralised backend to be able to improve the centralised machine learning model.
Additional information	-
Actor	GST
Priority	Should
Success Criteria	The centralised model has been updated with information from edge device models.
Expected delivery date	M36

Table 68 - Requirements UC#5-RE-09

Field	Definition
ID	UC#5-RE-09

Title	A communication platform is required
Level of detail	Stakeholder
Type	FUNC
Description	Occasionally, a data communication platform should be available to communicate with edge devices and allow to transfer information of low priority to centralised infrastructure.
Additional information	-
Actor	GST
Priority	Should
Success Criteria	Centralised infrastructure can communicate with edge devices.
Expected delivery date	M36

3.5.4 Description of datasets

This section contains tables that include descriptions of the datasets for the scenarios of this UC as described in the previous sections.

Table 69 - Dataset UC#5-DS-01

Field	Definition
ID	UC#5-DS-01
Title	Denmark's Depth Model
Description	A publicly available national Danish 50-metre average depth model
Owner	Danish Geodata Agency
Licence/Privacy	Open
Data type	Web services and file download
Type of Process (Stream or Static data)	OGC Web services and file downloads
Data Format	GeoTIFF and OGC Web services
Data Store	Internal Danish Geodata Agency storage
Recommended API	File download and web services
Data Volume	Less and 1 GB
Data Velocity	No automatic data update

Documentation	Public documentation is available from data access source.
Data Origin	Compiled depth model from Historic nautical charts Digitised depth soundings Single-beam depth soundings Multi-beam depth soundings
Will you reuse any existing data? If YES, which data and how?	Internal Danish Geodata Agency depth data used for nautical charts
Methodologies for data collection/generation	Data collected by Danish Navy and private contractors
Metadata and standards	Depth data model will consist of the following layers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Depth ● Data source ● Collection year
For whom might the dataset be useful?	The dataset may be useful for anyone working with maritime data related to the Danish Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ)
Data access, sharing and licensing	Public available from https://dataforsyningen.dk/data/4817
Security needs/legal issues	Data is averaged depth data in a 50-metre grid. Data is NOT safe for navigation.
Class	Public

Table 70 - Dataset UC#5-DS-02

Field	Definition
ID	UC#5-DS-02
Title	Simulated CSB data from AIS and UC#5-DS-01
Description	Data sets for simulating true CSB data. Simulated CSB data is generated from public available AIS data (https://www.soefartsstyrelsen.dk/sikkerhed-til-soes/sejladsinformation/ais-data) and Denmark's Depth Model (UC#5-DS-01) Due to the limited quantities of collected CSB data (UC#5-DS-03) and to overcome restrictions of licences of CSB, this data set is introduced to be able to provide large quantities of simulated CSB data, to serve as foundation for training machine learning models.
Owner	Danish Geodata Agency
Licence/Privacy	Danish Geodata Agency,

Data type	File
Type of Process (Stream or Static data)	Static, generated on demand
Data Format	CSV
Data Store	Internal GST, shared with AIT
Recommended API	Internal Danish Geodata Agency storage
Data Volume	Approximately 10 GB compressed, 50 GB uncompressed
Data Velocity	Generated on demand
Documentation	There is a readme along the data that explains its origin and datastructure
Data Origin	Public available AIS data (https://www.soefartsstyrelsen.dk/sikkerhed-til-soes/sejladsinformation/ais-data) and Denmark's Depth Model (UC#5-DS-01)
Will you reuse any existing data? If YES, which data and how?	AIS data and UC#5-DW-01.
Methodologies for data collection/generation	Internal GST developed data simulator
Metadata and standards	Described in readme.
For whom might the dataset be useful?	Others reproducing UC#5 results
Data access, sharing and licensing	Can be shared
Security needs/legal issues	This is NOT CSB data but fused data from two separate data sets. Data should not be used without a clear understanding of the limitations of this generated dataset.
Class	Internal

Table 71 - Dataset UC#5-DS-03

Field	Definition
ID	UC#5-DS-03
Title	Crowd-Sourced Bathymetry Data (CSB)
Description	Depth data collected while testing UC

Owner	Danish Geodata Agency
Licence/Privacy	Danish Geodata Agency, licence is TBD
Data type	File
Type of Process (Stream or Static data)	Stream
Data Format	CSV
Data Store	
Recommended API	Internal Danish Geodata Agency storage
Data Volume	Less than 1 GB
Data Velocity	
Documentation	-
Data Origin	Sea trial collected GNSS and depth sensor data
Will you reuse any existing data? If YES, which data and how?	Data collected while performing UC#5
Methodologies for data collection/generation	Data collected by use case during
Metadata and standards	To be described
For whom might the dataset be useful?	Others reproducing UC#5 results
Data access, sharing and licensing	Data cannot be shared without permissions from the Danish Defence.
Security needs/legal issues	Data cannot be shared without permissions from the Danish Defence.
Class	Internal

3.5.5 Current infrastructure

For this use case currently, two prototype edge devices have been developed in collaboration with Sternula A/S. These devices consist of Raspberry Pi 4 compute modules and are embedded with firmware providing connectivity via different mediums (Wi-Fi, mobile, satellite). The communication path, managed by Sternula A/S, provides a secure and versatile data flow from the edge nodes to a centralised computational platform.

4. Workshops results

As outlined above, the MOBISPACES project proposes a proactive and co-creative approach among partners. The aim is to ensure that in each UC the project requirements are well defined and meet the needs of the stakeholders. For these reasons, co-creation workshops were organised in conjunction with the General Assemblies to facilitate the exchange of ideas and refinement of the different aspects of the UCs. The insights provided at these events are detailed below.

4.1 Vienna

During the MOBISPACES General Assembly meeting in Vienna on 23-24 January 2023, a live Q&A session was conducted to collect the most important requirements of the UCs, so as to also better delineate the architecture. The contents of the requirements thus collected were then harmonised and included in the first version of this Deliverable series, i.e. D6.1. This first workshop allowed us to understand the real needs and aspects that need to be explored by the partners.

4.2 Lisbon

During the MOBISPACES General Assembly meeting in Lisbon on 4-6 July 2023, a workshop dedicated to co-creation moments was held.

The reference context in which these moments take place is that of the project in which the general architecture has achieved a better definition through the work of Work Package 2, just as Work Packages 3, 4 and 5 have achieved a clearer vision of the main architectural pillars developed within them.

For these reasons, it was decided to structure the workshop through two main moments to which the participants' attention was directed: the review of user stories and the creation of sketches that could pave the way towards the pipelining of the different tools within the UCs. The following subsections delve into both of these moments: the first introduces the shared theory with which it was decided to proceed with the revision of the user stories, while the second shares the (more or less successful) attempts at sketches in which the partners ventured during the second phase of the workshop.

4.2.1 User Stories: a refinement through the INVEST criterion

According to the Agile/Scrum methodology, each individual User Story is referable to a micro-functionality and the format used to describe it follows this logic:

*As **person/role X** I want **functionality Y** so I get **business benefit Z***

This structure makes it possible to understand:

- Which functionality needs to be developed
- Why it needs to be developed (the business benefit)

But when is a User Story really well written? To answer this question and try to define in the best possible way what a User Story should be, the Agile/Scrum methodology provides the INVEST criterion, the name of which is an acronym made up of the initial letters of the six

fundamental characteristics that must be fulfilled in order to try to have the best possible User Story:

- Independent
- Negotiable
- Valuable
- Estimable
- Small (or Sized Appropriately)
- Testable

For teams developing software according to the Agile methodology, this criterion helps to create the User Stories that populate the 'living document' par excellence, the so-called *backlog*. The meanings of these six aspects are explained below..

Independent.

This is difficult to achieve but absolutely essential. In detail, it must be avoided as far as possible to introduce dependencies between stories because it must be possible to reprioritise them in order to develop them in a different and more functional order to maximise work. The idea is to be able to develop stories according to value and not prioritise them because they are technically linked to other stories.

Negotiable.

User Stories are reported through “statements” usually on “cards” or “post-it” but should not be interpreted as armoured contracts given to developers! Product owners and developers must negotiate the details: clarify the requirement and the associated commitment. Example: "As X I must be able to print report Y in order to be able to examine data Z". What does this mean? Do you want a PrintScreen on screen or a report with customisable header and footer?

Valuable.

Business benefit always needs a super clear definition. In this way, the correct priority can be assigned to the functionality. In accordance with IETF RFC 2119⁷, priority levels can be defined as follows:

1. MUST / MUST NOT – it is an absolute requirement/prohibition
2. SHOULD / SHOULD NOT – it means “recommended” or not
3. MAY – it means “optional”

Estimable.

It is necessary for a User Story to be estimable from the point of view of the effort required to develop it. This helps prioritise it on the basis of a compromise (trade-off) based on a correct balance between effort (the estimate) and business benefit.

Small (or Sized Appropriately).

Small user stories are easier to estimate and test. They are easier to place within a development plan, but this does not mean that 'the smaller the better': a story that requires very little in terms of development, e.g., a few hours, might paradoxically take longer to write, analyse and follow up than to develop!

⁷ Source: <https://www.ietf.org/rfc/rfc2119.txt>

Testable.

If a User Story cannot be verified, then it can never be classified as finished. So, before the whole work can be considered as done, it is important to make sure that a criterion is in place to assess it as such, and KPIs can provide help in this sense.

These aspects guided the discussion during the first part of the co-creation workshop and enabled all participants to make suggestions regarding the User Stories and allow the UCs' partners to take note of them. The results of these reworkings enabled the updating of the corresponding tables in the appendix.

4.2.2 Sketches: first steps towards flow-like diagrams and tools pipelining

This second phase exploits the theory of sketches, as illustrated in Section 2, to begin to address the creation of flow-like diagrams for the UCs scenarios and which can involve the different tools developed by the partners within the MOBISPACES project. Below are the sketches made by hand and in less than five minutes by the participants in the different UCs. This work was useful so that the architectures of the Use Cases could be better defined: the improved and digitally realised diagrams were then fed into Deliverable D6.4, where they were explained in greater detail. Overall, the co-creation activities proved useful in order to support different aspects related to Work Package 6 and consequently to the implementation of the Use Cases tasks.

Figure 16 - UC #1 sketch

Figure 17 - UC #2 sketch

Figure 18 - UC #3 sketch

Figure 19 - UC #4 sketch

Figure 20 - UC #5 sketch

4.3 Future planning

Figure 14 illustrates at a high level the planning of the working group involved in the UCs-related co-creation workshops.

Prior to the release of each co-creation-related Deliverable, workshops were planned with dedicated sessions during the General Assemblies in Vienna, Lisbon and Naples, the results of which will be part of Deliverables D6.1, D6.2 and D6.3 respectively.

The purpose of each of these workshops is to fine-tune the data, user stories and functional and non-functional requirements, scenarios and objectives of each of the UCs. Therefore, the co-creation workshops will provide for the direct involvement of all the participants of each individual UC, who will be able to exchange ideas, identify and discuss problems as well as suggest solutions both between similar (terrestrial scenarios or maritime scenarios) and different domains.

Workshops will always be conducted in a hybrid mode, allowing both physical and remote participation in order to involve as many partners as possible. Modes of interaction will include the possibility of providing contributions both through traditional means (pen and paper) and through digital tools, generally considering the former as initial versions provided as hints during live events and the latter as more settled if not final versions.

In parallel, as an established practice, there will be periodic remote meetings to review progress, discuss emerging needs and problems, and ensure alignment of stakeholders' needs through continuous feedback.

Finally, after the release of the set of Deliverables, there will be remote validation of the results obtained and organised within the MOBISPACEs project platform.

Figure 21 - Co-creation workshops planning

4.3.1 Naples: a preview

The next co-creation workshop will include a general review of the KPIs of the UCs, deepening the interlocutions already initiated and further refining the results obtained so far and summarised in the tables below.

Table 72 - UC #1 iRoute KPIs refinement

KPI ID	KPI Phrasing	Interpretation
a)	Improved performance in re-scheduling the service to peak period (journey time > 75%)	Calling 'journey time' the time it takes for a bus to travel in a reserved bus lane, the KPI aims to achieve adherence to the schedule at peak times for more than 3 out of 4 buses travelling in the reserved bus lane. The adherence is measured checking if the real stop times are similar to the scheduled stop times with a tolerance of 3 minutes.
b)	Improved performance in re-scheduling the service to peak period (traffic time >75%)	Calling 'traffic time' the time it takes a bus to travel in city traffic, the KPI aims to achieve adherence to the schedule at peak times for more than 3 out of 4 buses travelling in city traffic. The adherence is measured checking if the real stop times are similar to the scheduled stop times with a tolerance of 3 minutes.
c)	Reduction of bus waiting for end-users/Bus punctuality >90%	Considering a line L, we call t_s^N and t_s^{N-1} the arrival times at stop s scheduled for the bus N of line L and for the preceding bus N-1 of the same line. $t_d = t_s^N - t_s^{N-1}$ is the difference, that is the bus frequency and the maximum time a user should wait at the stop. We call punctual a bus that comes at the stop s at the effective time t_e^N so that $t_e^N \leq t_s^N + \frac{t_d}{2}$. Thus, if the bus arrives after more than one and half the frequency, the transit is not regular. The regularity of the waiting time must be respected for more than 90% of cases.
d)	Accessibility of real-time information for better performing the connection with intermodality/other services provided and accessibility of real-time information to passengers > 95%	A MOBISPACEs Dashboard can inform real-time passengers on a bus about their estimated arrival at an important interchange stop, so that they can properly organise their connection with intermodality/other services. The prototype may cover AMT e-lines 3 and its interchanges with train stations Genova Principe, Genova Sampierdarena, Genova Cornigliano and Genova Sestri Ponente and/or AMT e-lines 3, 8, 63 and their interchanges with train station Genova Sampierdarena.
e)	Optimization of maintenance/repairing services >85%	The maintenance here mentioned regards electric buses' batteries. The analysis must identify the battery behaviours that do not follow the average behaviour (e.g. too fast decrease or too low recharge) in order that the buses can be checked to take corrective actions. The 85% of the considered buses must have a regular battery behaviour.

f)	Economic efficiency of all routes >70%	We may consider that in 70% of cases the e-bus must end its service with a correct amount of battery, neither too much (risk of waste) nor too little (risk of remaining without battery).
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Table 73 - UC #2 SmartSense KPIs refinement

KPI ID	KPI Phrasing	Interpretation
a)	Accurate and realistic input values for the traffic management system and air quality dispersion calculation (target: 10% emission reduction, baseline: locally measured data)	(target: showcase achievability of 10% emission reduction, baseline: locally measured data)
b)	Identification of A/Q hotspots (target: increase in recorded hotspots by means of A/Q monitoring using sensors, baseline: currently monitored and recorded data)	No further details are deemed necessary.
c)	More effective incorporation of environmental aspects by strategic traffic planners (target: use of A/Q data for traffic decision-making)	Facilitate incorporation of environmental aspects by strategic traffic planners (target: use of A/Q data for traffic decision-making)

Table 74 - UC #3 VesselTracker KPIs refinement

KPI ID	KPI Phrasing	Interpretation
a)	Data to object association accuracy >85%	Associating correctly data coming from Radio Frequency sources with AIS, i.e., assigning targets (vessels) detected from RF to known AIS tracks. We'll validate through ground truth, i.e., MarineTraffic AIS data by artificially removing the ID of the ship.
b)	Data to track association accuracy >80%	Each edge device has a limited scope, i.e., it might be the case that it tracks part of the trajectories of certain vessels. For this reason, we will perform the track-to-track operation after the position-to-track association (described in the previous KPI). This operation associates tracks (sub-trajectories) with other tracks. The output will be the global trajectories (entire trajectories of vessels coming from all edge devices). This KPI measures the accuracy achieved by performing this operation.

c)	Data to server flow reduction >30%	In this use case, we attempt to push as much computation effort as possible to the edge device in order to reduce data flow from the edge devices to the server. This KPI measures how we benefit from edge computing in terms of data flow to the server.
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Table 75 - UC #4 VesselEdge KPIs refinement

KPI ID	KPI Phrasing	Interpretation
a)	Successful deployment of a novel smart AIS system that pre-processes the raw AIS data stream and transmits the key information (local model) back to the control room (target: deployments on 3 ships, baseline: current vessel AIS systems are only used for on-board situation awareness)	No further details are deemed necessary.
b)	Extended AIS coverage beyond the reach of coastal AIS antennas (target: extend AIS coverage on-demand by linking sensors on-board of moving vessels, baseline: current terrestrial AIS coverage at the use case location)	No further details are deemed necessary.

Table 76 - UC #5 CrowdSeaMapping KPIs refinement

KPI ID	KPI Phrasing	Interpretation
a)	Utilise CSB data for detecting imprecisions to existing nautical charts where depth measured from sensors does not match with charted depths (such findings would be of highly importance in particular if shallower depths are found than what is charted) >70%	Quality of anomaly detection: utilise CSB data for detecting discrepancies in the existing depth model where depth measured from ships sensors does not match with the depth model. At least 70% of discrepancies detected by machine learning model should be correct (i.e. true positives, based on domain expert feedback).
b)	Generic verification of charts, where larger areas of CSB data is compared to existing charts (this could	Verification of existing depth model: more than 90% of CSB data (from actual ships) will be compared to existing depth models (to serve as a base for possible prioritisation of resurveying efforts).

	be useful to help prioritise where to put effort in resurveying and the seabed) >90%	
c)	Consider utilising CSB data for actually charting sea areas where no surveying have been performed or quality of existing surveys are questionable >50% of data deriving from CSB	Identification of areas of low trustworthiness: more than 50% of CSB data in uncharted / questionable areas will be evaluated to identify areas of low trustworthiness.

5. Conclusions

The major outcome of this deliverable is to provide guidelines for co-creation activities related to the different UC scenarios identified within the project. Also, another outcome is to collect and collate the results of co-creation workshops to improve processes within the project. In brief, this aids to bridge the gap between UC stories and the implementation activities followed by the technical partners in the project.

As such, the purpose of the deliverable is twofold: on the one hand it provides an overview of the theoretical approaches of co-creation and the impact on UI/UX design processes and related tools, and on the other hand it provides a detailed view of the project's UCs. For each UC, the objectives are presented, followed by scenarios and then user requirements. Subsequently, descriptions of the necessary datasets per UC are provided, and - finally - the current infrastructure pertinent to each UC is recorded.

The organisation of a series of workshops has been planned in correspondence with each General Assembly meeting. Focus groups for each UC have been built, so as to ensure that the feedback obtained through the co-creation process can be as closely aligned as possible with the different requirements of the UCs: this aspect is duly taken into account by also providing individual meetings for each UC so that the needs of all partners can continue to be met.

Overall, this deliverable is crucial for achieving the outputs of the MOBISPACES project, adopting a user-driven approach, and ensuring that project outcomes meet the needs of stakeholders identified in the UCs and related to all the activities put in place. The commitment to collaboration and co-creation throughout these workshops and focus groups will ensure that all UC representatives can clearly express their viewpoint and are adequately involved in the decision-making process.

6. References

- Knapp, J., Zeratsky, J., & Kowitz, B. (2016). *Sprint: How to solve big problems and test new ideas in just five days*. Simon and Schuster.
- O'Hern, M. S., & Rindfleisch, A. (2017). Customer co-creation: A typology and research agenda. *Review of marketing research*, 84-106.
- Ramaswamy, V., & Ozcan, K. (2014). *The co-creation paradigm*. Stanford University Press.

7. Appendix

7.1 User Stories

User Story ID#	Use Case	Leader	As person/role X...	... I want functionality Y...	... so I get business benefit Z.	Independent?	Negotiable?	Valuable?	Estimable?	Small?	Testable?
US1_01	iRoute	AMT	Fleet Maintainer	I want to be able to retrieve the data stored in the archives of the installed ITSs	so I can make use of better operational and maintenance tools	Yes	Requirements defined	Must	Completed by M36	Yes	KPIs & Units of measurement defined/under definition
US1_02	iRoute	AMT	Data Analyst	I want to be able to analyse and combine fleet data	so I can get a thorough understanding of fleet behaviour	Yes	Requirements defined	Must	Completed by M36	Yes	KPIs & Units of measurement defined/under definition
US1_03	iRoute	AMT	Service Manager	I want to be able to extract insights from fleet data	so I can have decision support and optimise fleet allocation	Yes	Requirements defined	Must	Completed by M36	Yes	KPIs & Units of measurement defined/under definition
US2_01	Smart Sense	BO SC H	Environmental officer	I want to have accurate and reliable air quality measurement data at defined location	so I can monitor the air quality	Yes	Requirements defined	Must	Completed by M36	Yes	KPIs & Units of measurement defined
US2_02	Smart Sense	BO SC H	Environmental officer	I want to have accurate and reliable air quality heat maps covering the total area of interest	so I can monitor the air quality of the total area	Yes	Requirements defined	Should	Completed by M36	Yes	KPIs & Units of measurement defined
US2_03	Smart Sense	BO SC H	Traffic authority	I want to have accurate and reliable traffic and vehicle flow information	so I can monitor the traffic situation on the complete road network and can define measures to reduce its emission impact	Yes	Requirements defined	Should	Completed by M36	Yes	KPIs & Units of measurement defined

US3_01	Vessel Tracker	MT	Maritime intelligence Data engineer	I want to use and process vessel tracking data in a decentralised way	so that I can monitor vessels in real-time while reducing the data flow to the server	Yes	Requirements defined	Must	Completed by M12	Yes	KPIs & Units of measurement defined
US3_02	Vessel Tracker	MT	Maritime intelligence user	I want to be able to combine AIS with other sources	so that I am able to track "dark vessels", i.e., vessels that cannot be tracked using one source (AIS) but can be tracked using another source (radar)	Yes	Requirements defined	Must	Completed by M24	To be split	KPIs & Units of measurement defined
US3_03	Vessel Tracker	MT	Maritime intelligence user	I want to know which targets detected in RF data correspond to known AIS tracks	So that I can fill in missed positions via AIS and detect dark vessels	Yes	Requirements defined	Must	Completed by M24	To be split	KPIs & Units of measurement defined
US3_04	Vessel Tracker	MT	Maritime intelligence user	I want to see vessel tracks coming from different sources (AIS, RF) on the map, along with statistics about fused tracks and vessels detected in each source	So that I can easily see the enriched information (unified tracks coming from RF and AIS data) and statistics about dark vessels (un-associated RF detections)	Yes	Requirements defined	Must	Completed by M24	To be split	Not yet
US3_05	Vessel Tracker	MT	Maritime intelligence user	I want to see arbitrary information about the port/marine that the vessels reside in, by fusing AIS and RF data with other open data in real time	So that I can have more context of the facilities of the port/marinas that the vessels reside in	Yes	Requirements defined	May	Completed by M24	Yes	Not yet
US4_01	Vessel Edge	FRQ	Rescue Mission Coordinator	I want to have visibility of the situation on scene even if I do not have AIS coverage for the place of incident	so that I have the full situational awareness when coordinating a rescue mission	Yes	Requirements defined	Must	Completed by M36	Yes	KPIs & Units of measurement defined
US4_02	Vessel Edge	FRQ	Maritime Agency	I want to be able to share "behavioural learning" from my area with other neighbouring agency without sharing the actual AIS data (and vice-versa)	so that overall my system can provide better anomaly detection for decision support	Yes	Requirements defined	Should	Completed by M36	Yes	KPIs & Units of measurement defined

US5_001	CrowdSea Mapping	GS T	Mariner	I want to know in real-time when measured depths are less than existing depths from a depth model	so I get improved safety when navigating at the sea	Yes	Requirements defined	Must	Completed by M24	Yes	KPIs & Units of measurement defined
US5_002	CrowdSea Mapping	GS T	Surveyor	I want to validate existing depth models	so I get a tool for determining where future surveying should be planned	Yes	Requirements defined	Must	Completed by M36	Yes	KPIs & Units of measurement defined
US5_003	CrowdSea Mapping	GS T	Mariner	I want to have improved depth data coverage	so I get improved nautical products for safer navigation with extended coverage	Yes	Requirements defined	Must	Completed by M36	Yes	KPIs & Units of measurement defined

7.2 Use Cases Requirements

Requirement ID#	US ID# Reference	Leader	Technical Partner	Requirements	Scenario(s) reference(s) ID#	Dataset(s) reference(s) ID#	Priority
UC#1-RE-01	US1_001	AMT	ENG	Data ingestion from AMT ITSs to cloud	UC#1-SCE-01	UC#1-DS-01, UC#1-DS-02, UC#1-DS-03	Must
UC#1-RE-02	US1_001	AMT	ENG	Data ingestion from cloud (external data) to cloud	UC#1-SCE-01	UC#1-DS-01, UC#1-DS-02, UC#1-DS-03	Must
UC#1-RE-03	US1_001	AMT	ENG	Data-enriched control panel for operation and maintenance	UC#1-SCE-01	UC#1-DS-01, UC#1-DS-02, UC#1-DS-03	Should
UC#1-RE-04	US1_002	AMT	ENG	Ability to perform analytics in the cloud on internal data	UC#1-SCE-02	UC#1-DS-01, UC#1-DS-02, UC#1-DS-03	Must
UC#1-RE-05	US1_002	AMT	ENG	Possibility of enriching internal data analytics with external data (e.g. meteorological)	UC#1-SCE-02	UC#1-DS-01, UC#1-DS-02, UC#1-DS-03	Should
UC#1-RE-06	US1_003	AMT	ENG	Overview of fleet data via dashboard	UC#1-SCE-03	UC#1-DS-01, UC#1-DS-02, UC#1-DS-03	Must
UC#1-RE-	US1_003	AMT	ENG	Elaboration of average values and estimates of data needed for allocation (e.g.	UC#1-SCE-03	UC#1-DS-01, UC#1-DS-	Must

07				battery level)		02, UC#1-DS-03	
UC#1-RE-08	US1_003	AMT	ENG	Display of alerts and suggestions	UC#1-SCE-03	UC#1-DS-01, UC#1-DS-02, UC#1-DS-03	May
UC#2-RE-01	US2_001, US2_002	BOSCH	EMIS	Measurements of air quality	UC#2-SCE-02	UC#2-DS-01	Must
UC#2-RE-02	US2_003	BOSCH	EMIS	Generate area covering emission data for every hour	UC#2-SCE-01	UC#2-DS-02	Must
UC#2-RE-03	US2_001	BOSCH	EMIS	Validate measurements against defined estimated accuracy for each measurement location	UC#2-SCE-02	UC#2-DS-02	Should
UC#2-RE-04	US2_001	BOSCH	EMIS	Implementation of environmental sensitive traffic management	all	all	May
UC#3-RE-01	US3_001	MT	MT	Real-time AIS data ingestion on the edge device	UC#3-SCE-01	UC#3-DS-01	Must
UC#3-RE-02	US3_001	MT	MT	Real-time AIS processing on the edge device	UC#3-SCE-01	UC#3-DS-01	Must
UC#3-RE-03	US3_001	MT	OKYS	Data cleaning for AIS data	UC#3-SCE-01	UC#3-DS-01	Must
UC#3-RE-04	US3_002	MT	MT	Real-time RF data ingestion on the edge device	UC#3-SCE-02	UC#3-DS-02	Must
UC#3-RE-05	US3_002	MT	MT	RF data processing on edge	UC#3-SCE-02	UC#3-DS-02	Must
UC#3-RE-06	US3_003	MT	MT	Position-to-track association on edge in real-time	UC#3-SCE-02	UC#3-DS-01, UC#3-DS-02	Must
UC#3-RE-07	US3_003	MT	MT	Track-to-track association on edge in real-time	UC#3-SCE-03	UC#3-DS-01, UC#3-DS-02	Must
UC#3-RE-08	US3_004	MT	NETU	Visualisation of vessel tracking data coming from different sources, associated tracks on the map and statistics	UC#3-SCE-04	UC#3-DS-01, UC#3-DS-02	Must
UC#3-RE-	US3_005	MT	UPRC	Semantic modelling of maritime data and semantic data fusion with arbitrary open	UC#3-SCE-05	UC#3-DS-01, UC#3-DS-	May

09				data		02	
UC#4-RE-01	US4_001	FRQ	FRQ	Real-time AIS data ingestion on the edge device	UC#4-SCE-01	UC#4-DS-01	Must
UC#4-RE-02	US4_001	FRQ	AIT	Real-time AIS processing on the edge device	UC#4-SCE-01	UC#4-DS-01	Must
UC#4-RE-03	US4_001	FRQ	AIT/ULB	"Data reduction" (trajectory compression) on the edge device	UC#4-SCE-01	UC#4-DS-01	Must
UC#4-RE-04	US4_001	FRQ	FRQ	A communication platform is required, enabling communication even while vessel is at sea	UC#4-SCE-01	UC#4-DS-01	Must
UC#4-RE-05	US4_001	FRQ	FRQ	Visualisation of vessel data coming from different VesselEdge sources (trajectory reconstruction/recovery and/or learnings)	UC#4-SCE-01	UC#4-DS-01	Must
UC#4-RE-06	US4 (all)	FRQ	FRQ	Vessels and area for testing available	UC#4-SCE-01	UC#4-DS-01	Must
UC#4-RE-07	US4_001	FRQ	FRQ	Container environment on Edge Device	UC#4-SCE-01	UC#4-DS-01	Must
UC#4-RE-08	US4_002	FRQ	FRQ	Real-time AIS data ingestion on shore	UC#4-SCE-02	UC#4-DS-01	Should
UC#4-RE-09	US4_002	FRQ	AIT	Real-time AIS processing on shore	UC#4-SCE-02	UC#4-DS-01	Should
UC#4-RE-10	US4_002	FRQ	AIT	Federated learning (Local model / Anomaly Detection)	UC#4-SCE-02	UC#4-DS-01	Should
UC#4-RE-11	US4_002	FRQ	AIT	Data format for sharing learnings (anomaly detection) with other agency	UC#4-SCE-02	UC#4-DS-01	Should
UC#5-RE-01	US5_001	GST	GST	Real time GNSS sensor data ingestion on the edge device	UC#5-SCE-01	UC#5-DS-03	Must
UC#5-RE-02	US5_001	GST	GST	Real time depth sensor data ingestion on the edge device	UC#5-SCE-01	UC#5-DS-03	Must
UC#5-RE-	US5_001	GST	AIT	Real time data evaluation using machine learning model on edge device	UC#5-SCE-02	UC#5-DS-03	Must

03							
UC#5-RE-04	US5_001	GST	NETU	Visualise machine learning sensor evaluation output	UC#5-SCE-01	all	May
UC#5-RE-05	US5_002, US5_003	GST	GST	CSB data available for edge device	UC#5-SCE-02, UC#5-SCE-03	UC#5-DS-03	Must
UC#5-RE-06	US5_002, US5_003	GST	AIT	CSB data evaluation using machine learning model	UC#5-SCE-02, UC#5-SCE-03	UC#5-DS-03	Must
UC#5-RE-07	US5_002	GST	GST	A communication platform is required, enabling communication even while vessel is at sea	UC#5-SCE-02	UC#5-DS-03	Should
UC#5-RE-08	US5_003	GST	AIT	Update federated machine learning model with CSB data	UC#5-SCE-03	UC#5-DS-03	Should
UC#5-RE-09	US5_003	GST	GST	A communication platform is required	UC#5-SCE-03	UC#5-DS-03	Should